

The Biodiversity Crisis

A Perspective From Ireland

The Dark Sky over Earth's Limb - [NASA](#)

Anto Kerins
26 May 26

For

Joshua and Jacob

A T Kerins©

Preface

The Earth's limb is the edge of our world, the luminous envelope of gases shielding life on the planet from the cold, dark spaces beyond. It is the Earth's protective halo taking its name from the Latin word *limbus*, meaning border.

Its lower layer is the troposphere. Above that is the blue layer or stratosphere beyond which the limb gradually fades into the blackness of space.¹

Every day we travel at great speed through the universe and journey immense distances but feel none of it. Underneath this halo of light, this border, lies the natural world – Earth's protected home.

This report looks at the crisis in the natural world, in biodiversity and provides an indication of some the main things we can do about it.

As the crisis has unfolded some suggest we consider a back-up plan into the future. This has become a theme in late-career scientific warnings. For example, Stephen Hawking's final book says 'we are running out of space and the only places to go to are other worlds.' Late-career scientists often feel they have nothing left to lose, are not tied to an institution or funding patron and feel free to be frank.²

Elon Musk, the space entrepreneur and SpaceX founder, says we have two options. First, 'we stay on Earth forever, and then there will be some eventual extinction event. I do not have an immediate doomsday prophecy, but eventually, history suggests, there will be some doomsday event. The alternative is to become a space-bearing civilization and a multi-planetary species, which I hope you would agree is the right way to go.'³

Looking at Ireland in the north-west corner of Europe, the report brings the local situation into play to help us understand the crisis more clearly and finds there is nothing here we cannot fix. The real issue is that we often do not fully realise what is needed and how essential it is do the right thing.

No one really wants to go space travelling. A holiday perhaps but not forever.

Anto Kerins

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report examines the biodiversity crisis and how we can respond to it. It reviews recent developments in Ireland and outlines the lessons we can draw from these to help us address the crisis everywhere.

The introduction locates the island of Ireland and our country focus, Ireland, and outlines the importance of the natural world to our health and wellbeing, our economy, society and very existence.

The challenging trends in biodiversity globally and in protected areas, the tropics, and the EU are discussed along with Ireland's poor record on biodiversity despite being one of the richest countries in the world and one of the most highly regarded for its natural environment and landscape.

Following this we examine the case of the North Bull Island Nature Reserve to help us better understand the nature of the challenge on the ground. This small reserve is one of the most important city wildlife spaces in the world and the most designated site in Ireland. However, its biodiversity has continued to weaken over time and understanding why this is still happening helps us to better understand the nature and form of the challenge we face.

We then look at the international and EU context for biodiversity and at the EU's ambition on biodiversity and ask, can Ireland match this ambition?

Here, we look at recent developments in Ireland: its parliament's declaration of a climate and biodiversity emergency in 2019, Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity in 2022, joint parliamentary committee on the topic in December 2023, and 4th National Biodiversity Action Plan published in January 2024. These are important developments. However, in spite of these developments, Ireland's biodiversity remains under significant pressure. Why is this and what can be done about it?

Here we discuss various ways of dealing with the crisis and improve on what has been done to date.

At national level we propose the idea of a National Forum on Biodiversity and Climate Resilience centred through the political system.

At neighbourhood level we proposed a UK-Ireland Biodiversity and Climate Resilience Unit for the Great Britain and Ireland Archipelago.

Both recommendations are worth considering everywhere, if we are to deal more effectively with the crisis.

The reflection section, among other things, introduces the concept of the safe surface of the natural world and states that the main reason for this report is to help strengthen it.

We conclude by looking to the future.

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INTRODUCTION

Island of Ireland

The island of Ireland is located in the North Atlantic in north-west Europe between 51.4° and 55.4° latitude and 5.4° and 10.7° longitude with its nearest neighbour Great Britain, on its eastern side.

It is characterised by a fertile central lowland surrounded by coastal mountain ranges and an indented coastline — especially along the west — that has a variety of bays, peninsulas, and cliffs. Its geographical location exposes it to the Gulf Stream or North Atlantic Drift, giving it a temperate maritime climate with relatively cool summers, mild winters, and frequent rainfall.

[EU-Ireland: Wikimedia Commons](#)

Geographically it stands at a gateway between Europe and the Americas and acts as an important hub for transatlantic trade and connectivity.

Surrounded by the Irish Sea to the east, the Celtic Sea to the south and the Atlantic to the west, it is divided politically into Ireland, an independent Republic, and Northern Ireland which is part of the UK.

Ireland the country and focus of our study, covers about five-sixths of the island. With a population of 5.5 million it is one of the richest countries in the world. It is also one of the most highly regarded for its natural environment and landscape and is sometimes referred to as the Emerald Isle.⁴

Nature

Significant evidence has accumulated over the years indicating that nature is good for our health and wellbeing. For example, research studies have found that being out in nature is good for our cognitive function and brain activity. It has also been found to be beneficial for our blood pressure, mental health, physical activity and our sleep. In addition, green spaces have been found to positively influence children's development with opportunities for discovery, creativity, risk taking, mastery, and control. Nature has also been found to support improvements in our health, through providing opportunities for social engagement and physical activity.⁵

There is also evidence indicating that contact with nature is associated with both improved pregnancy outcomes for women along with reduced risk of cardiometabolic and neurodegenerative diseases for older people.⁶

More broadly, nature is essential for our economy and society where it provides food, water and air and we use the natural world for many of the goods and services we require. Nature, therefore, underpins our existence by supplying us with basic life support and many of the material goods that we need.

However, because nature is 'free', we often take it for granted and overexploit it. For example, we pollute our oceans, rivers and lakes, overfish our finite stocks, unnecessarily build on or near wetlands, and clear away forests without taking full account of the impact of these activities. By not being fully aware of nature's many benefits, we damage and erode the natural world without realising the social, economic and human costs involved.⁷

Trends

Nature is being eroded everywhere and the majority of indicators show a rapid decline in its health. This erosion has been significantly caused by human activity. First, we look at the global situation.

Global

According to research, 75% of the Earth's land surface has been significantly altered, 66% of its oceans are showing increased cumulative impacts, over 85% of wetlands have been lost and human activity now threatens more species with global extinction than ever before.

In addition, 25% of species in assessed animal and plant groups are threatened and around 1 million of them face extinction unless we take significant action.

The weakened fabric of the natural world is already affecting the economic stability of nations and regions and according to the evidence, solving these problems will not be achieved under current efforts but only through fundamental change in economic, social, political and technological factors.⁸

In the face of this challenge, the development and safeguarding of protected areas plays an important role in safeguarding nature. Protected Areas are clearly defined geographical spaces that are legally or officially designated, managed explicitly for conservation and recognised in national or supranational systems.

By contrast, Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures (OECMs) are geographically defined areas that are not officially designated as protected areas but still achieve effective, long-term conservation, often as a by-product of other goals. For example, some private lands or community-managed woodlands, although not registered as state nature reserves, are managed in a way that protects biodiversity. Other examples include military zones, sacred sites, and 'no-trawl' marine areas such as those around shipwrecks.⁹

Protected Areas

Establishing protected areas is one of the most effective ways to conserve nature and endangered species. A 2020 review states that 209,000 protected areas have been established

worldwide covering 15.4% of the world's terrestrial surface and 3.4% of its oceans.¹⁰ More recently, the *Protected Planet Report 2024* states that coverage has reached 17.6% of terrestrial and inland waters and 8.4% of marine and coastal areas.¹¹

An important development is the 30 by 30 initiative to designate 30% of Earth's land and ocean area as protected areas by 2030. The target was proposed by a group of scientists in a 2019 article where it recommended an increase in nature conservation in order to mitigate the impact of climate change.

The article states that 'efforts to stabilize the climate and avoid the undesirable ... warming will require a rapid reduction in land conversion and a moratorium by about 2035'. It advises that the way forward is to maintain and restore 'at least 50% of the Earth's land area as intact natural ecosystems, in combination with energy transition measures'.

It also maintains that since 'natural ecosystems are key to maintaining human prosperity in a warming world' conservation is 'critical' to dealing with the crisis and they refer here to the importance of natural forests, peatlands, tundra, mangroves, ancient grasslands, and the freshwater and marine realms, including the least disturbed wetlands and coastal habitats which they argue are superior for storing carbon than more disturbed sites. They regard the 30% target by 2030 'as a milestone' on the path towards the 50% target by 2050.¹²

The 30 by 30 target was officially adopted in December 2022, during the 15th Conference of the Parties (COP15) to the UN Convention on Biological Diversity in Montreal.

The 30 by 30 target was officially adopted in December 2022 as Target 3 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) during the UN Biodiversity Conference (COP15).¹³ This was an important development.

Protected areas lie at the heart of our efforts to safeguard nature and the services it provides and help conserve species, biodiversity and ecosystems.

Protected areas help us deal with climate change by holding about 15.2% of the Earth's terrestrial carbon stocks.¹⁴ Terrestrial *carbon stocks* refer to all carbon stored in land-based ecosystems, regardless of how fast or slow they might be restored if lost.

However, *irrecoverable carbon* stocks are a subset of terrestrial carbon, defined by time and climate urgency. These are carbon stocks stored in ecosystems that cannot be recovered within the timeframe needed to avoid dangerous climate change if they are released, typically regarded as by 2050.

Agriculture, logging and wildfires have caused considerable loss of irrecoverable carbon and the world's remaining stocks face continuing risks from land-use conversion and climate change. Therefore, safeguarding our existing stocks remain a major priority. At present about 23% of irrecoverable carbon stocks are still held in protected areas and these must be safeguarded through good policies and effective management.¹⁵

How Are Protected Areas Doing?

Although we would expect that biodiversity is doing well in protected areas we often do not know what is happening. This is because 4.78% of land and 1.26% of marine area is covered by protected areas where management effectiveness has been assessed and this is due to the

fact that most of the protected areas in the world have little or no oversight, enforcement, or active conservation.¹⁶

This phenomenon has led to the concept of 'paper parks' or 'paper reserves'. Although existing legally as protected areas, they have little or no capacity to protect. There is, therefore, an urgent need to enhance the effectiveness of existing reserves rather than focussing simply on the creation of new ones that may in the end turn out to be protected areas on paper.¹⁷

One study finds that about 70 per cent of marine protected areas, partially or totally fail to achieve their conservation goals.¹⁸ Another finds that 73% of protected areas, equal to three times the size of Japan, experienced habitat loss between 2003 and 2019 due to development expansion and other factors.

We now look at how biodiversity is doing in the protected areas in tropical forests, the EU and Ireland.

Tropical Forests: This part of nature has received much attention over the years. As a result a significant number of protected areas have been set up in tropical forests around the world.

Research shows, however, that protected areas in tropical forests are not doing well. One study of 60 reserves found that there was a noticeable variation in reserve health with about half of them experiencing a level of biodiversity erosion that was alarming. The 60 reserves were evenly stratified across the world's three major tropical forest regions: Africa, the Americas, and the Asia-Pacific region and included 36 countries all of which indicated a widespread decline in biodiversity.¹⁹

EU: Biodiversity has been doing poorly across the EU's terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems due to continuing pressures from production and consumption activities. For example, 81% of the EU's protected habitats are in a poor or bad state, 60-70% of soils degraded and 62% of water bodies in poor condition. In addition, between 1990 and 2023 the index of 168 common birds fell by 15% in the EU.²⁰

The EU recently reported that it is 'likely off track' to meet any of its four biodiversity and ecosystem-related monitoring targets by 2030. The targets are: to reverse the decline in populations of common birds, increase the degree of connectivity in forest ecosystems and legally protect at least 30% of its land area and 30% of its sea area by 2030. Therefore, while the EU has increased its protected areas numerically over time it is more important, in some respects, to improve biodiversity in the already established protection areas.²¹

Next, we look at how biodiversity is doing in Ireland.

Ireland: Only 13.95% of Ireland's land and 2.09% of its marine waters are covered by protected areas compared to the EU's 26.4% and 12.1%. This leaves Ireland's habitat protection at almost half the EU's terrestrial and one sixth of its maritime equivalent.²²

How are protected areas doing in Ireland? According to the latest research, 90% of its protected habitats on the EU Habitats Directive have an unfavourable status and 51% indicate ongoing decline. This is an increase from the previous findings of 85% and 46% respectively.²³

In addition, Ireland was also placed 13th from the bottom for biodiversity intactness in a list of 240 countries worldwide, leaving it in the lowest 6% of countries.²⁴

In addition, 30% of Ireland's protected species have an unfavourable status and over half of its native plant species have declined. More than half of its 100 bee species have declined substantially and 30% of these are threatened with extinction. Finally, 21% of its breeding birds and 52% of its key wintering bird species are in decline.²⁵

Therefore, not only has Ireland a relatively low proportion of protected areas with a high level of unfavourable status and a continuing downward trend in that status, its biodiversity intactness is particularly low by world standards.

Ireland, as we now see, faces a major biodiversity crisis of significant proportions. How, therefore, has it been dealing with this crisis? We look at this question later.

First, we ground our discussion on this question by considering the case of the North Bull Island Nature Reserve in Dublin city to help us better understand the nature of the challenge on the ground.

Then we consider the international, regional and EU context followed by a discussion of developments at national level in Ireland. Finally, we consider the crisis more broadly and ask how we might begin to resolve it.

CASE

North Bull Island

Bull Island is a low-lying sand spit in Dublin Bay formed after improvements were made to the port during the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. It contains a long sandy beach, a sand dune complex, areas of dune slacks and salt marsh along with extensive mudflats. The lagoon between the island and the mainland was divided in two by the 1960s construction of the causeway road. At about 5 km long and almost 1 km wide, part of its interior has been converted to two golf courses, both of which together cover a substantial part of the island.²⁶ See Appendix 1.

The island is subject to a constant cycle of erosion and growth and has experienced significant dune formation over the past 50 years. While the dune erosion tends to be cyclical the island's slow growth is expected to continue into the future.²⁷

It has a wealth of biodiversity. This includes several habitats and species in the EU Habitats Directive, by national and internationally important wintering waders and wildfowl and the presence of several rare listed plants. Because of this it is also an important site for education and science.

There are, in fact, two reserves on the island, comprising 1436 hectares in total.²⁸ For convenience, we refer here to the reserve in the singular.

Designations: The North Bull Island Nature Reserve is one of the most important city reserves in the world, the most designated site in Ireland and has accumulated a variety of national, European, and other designations.²⁹

Classified as a National Nature Reserve under Irish legislation and a Special Protection Area (SPA) under the EU Birds Directive, it is the focal point of the North Dublin Bay Special Area

of Conservation (SAC) under the EU Habitats Directive while also being the subject of a Special Amenity Area Order.³⁰

[North Bull Island](#)

It was also designated a Biosphere by UNESCO in 1981. This was superseded in 2015 with UNESCO's Dublin Bay Biosphere Reserve (DBBR) designation covering 305km² of marine and terrestrial habitat that includes North Bull Island along with conservation areas – Tolka and Baldoyle Estuaries, Howth Head, Dalkey Island, Killiney Hill and Booterstown Marsh. UNESCO's Biosphere Reserves are different than other protected areas in endeavouring to balance conservation with sustainable use and are designed through a community-based, integrated approach which focuses on interactions between core conservation zones, buffer zones and more intensively-used transition zones, which can include urban areas.³¹ Despite its many designations, its biodiversity has faced significant challenges over the years and the outlook into the future is uncertain.

Dublin City Council

The reserve is managed by Dublin City Council under its Parks, Biodiversity and Landscape Services division. However, its management, despite some good work over the years, has been a disappointment as we see below.

Irish Hare: The Irish Hare has become locally extinct on Bull Island with the last recorded siting in 2015. Found only on the island of Ireland, it is internationally important but in long-term decline and is, therefore, an important conservation species. In addition, its disappearance from the island may have long-term consequences where, according to one study, the 'natural process of dune stabilisation and plant succession is a threat to protected Annex 1 habitats'.³²

Little Tern: The Little Tern no longer breeds on the island. The reserve was previously one of the most important breeding sites in the country for Little Terns, Ireland's rarest breeding tern. Dublin City Council actively managed part of the northern tip of the island for the Little Tern, fencing it off and a temporary warden was employed in 1987 to facilitate breeding. However, breeding declined over time due to increased disturbance, predator impacts and possibly changes in substrate.³³

Dogs: Dogs are an invasive species in a protected area such as Bull Island and can negatively impact wildlife at multiple levels.³⁴

They can spread disease, harass and kill wildlife, force species to limit their habitat and reduce breeding rates. Dogs have been implicated in the extinction of 11 species worldwide and are considered a potential threat to over 188 additional species of concern. Consequently, dogs have large-scale effects in fragmented habitats like Bull Island.

Dog walking in nature areas has been found to leads to a 'dramatic reduction in bird diversity and abundance ... both in areas where dog walking is common and where dogs are prohibited'. This sort of finding helps us understand why 'conservation managers often ban dog walking ... fearing that wildlife will see dogs as potential predators and abandon their natural habitats'.³⁵

Dogs have been continually observed in and around Bull Island's sensitive habitats throughout the year with the majority off lead. One study identified 1,093 dogs during a twelve day and five nighttime observation period with almost 80 per cent of them off lead.³⁶

Because of the harm dogs cause to wildlife and because of their continual presence and abundance on the reserve, the Bull Island Nature Reserve is *not functionally protected*, and this situation is contrary to the designations and legislation that support its existence.³⁷

Safe Zones: There have been no safe zones over the years for ground nesting birds, unusual varieties such as Cuckoo, Short-Eared Owl, Ringed Plover, winter feeding birds, core ecosystems except for the Little Tern in 1987.

There has also been a lack of adequate signage and communications on best practices over the years with regard, for example, to nesting areas, rare birds, sensitive ecosystems, dogs, and cycling through sensitive ecosystems on the island.

However, Dublin City Council introduced a voluntary Visitor Access Management Plan on 1 May 2023. The main aim of the plan is to reduce disturbance to sensitive wildlife on the island by people and dogs.³⁸ Following this, it appointed five Conservation Park Rangers to cover the nature reserve and St Anne's Park nearby in September 2024.

Visitor Access Management Plan (Dublin City Council)³⁹

For the first time the reserve has an access framework for visitors and a dedicated group of Conservation Park Rangers supporting its requirements.⁴⁰ Anecdotal evidence so far, indicates some reduction in visitor and dog impacts on the saltmarsh. In addition, the visual presence and work of the Conservation Park Rangers seems to be having an impact. These are important developments.

Despite these improvements, ground nesting birds continue to be endangered by human activity and dogs continue to affect nesting, resting and feeding birds. In addition, many dog owners continue to leave their dogs off lead in the sensitive zones and ground nesting areas.

The continuing dangers to ground nesting birds on Bull Island and elsewhere has been well signposted in the literature. Bird populations continue to decline globally with losses recorded for many European breeding birds and habitat management measures have not resulted in widespread reversal of these declines. One study indicates that ground-nesting birds were 86 % more likely to decline than birds with other nesting strategies. This study discusses the impact of generalist predator abundance (principally red fox and species of the family Corvidae family) which is additional to the impact of human and dog pressure on reserves.⁴¹

A recent UK study found that most dogs were walked off the lead even with signs requesting that dogs should be kept on a lead. This resulted in up to a 21% increase in reserve area disturbed and in one reserve more than 90% of the area was disturbed by dogs, greatly eroding its conservation value.⁴²

A study commissioned by Dublin City Council states that zoning is 'only as good as the enforcement' that supports it and that although proper signage is important it is 'not a replacement for a strongly enforced no-go zone through wardening'.⁴³

Solutions are available, however, and there are a variety of successful visitor access arrangements for dog owners, including leash rules, restricted zones, seasonal access, and penalties for non-compliance.

For example, visitors to the heathland reserves of Bournemouth, Christchurch and Poole in Dorset, England must keep their dog on a lead under Public Spaces Protection Orders (PSPOs). In addition, each visitor must carry a poop scoop and disposable bags, clear up after their dog, and limit the number of dogs they bring. Ignoring a PSPO carries an on the spot fine of £100 or up to £1,000 in court.⁴⁴

In addition, in Salzgitter in Germany, anyone breaking the rules on compulsory dog leads in the city's nature reserves and conservation areas can be fined.⁴⁵

There are also widely available and established conservation solutions for providing safe nesting space for Little Terns, Ringed Plovers and others in similar ground nesting sites⁴⁶

Water Table & Golf Clubs: The reserve's water table has been affected over the years by the two golf clubs who use it for irrigation purposes. This negatively affects the dune slack habitats since the water table facilitates the existence of rare and protected plant species. The long term fall in water tables at similar sites across Europe has led to the loss of specialist dune slack flora and the invasion of coarse vegetation and scrub.⁴⁷

Discovery Centre Proposal

The most recent issue has been the council's proposal to build a Discovery Centre on the island that first appeared 13 years ago and that has since undergone debate, delays, and amendments and has yet to play out fully and has still not yet been submitted for decision to the planning authority, An Coimisiún Pleanála. A consideration of this saga, however, will tell us a lot about

the conflicting pressures on public officials and politicians in a time of biodiversity and climate resilience crisis.

Conceived as an education, exhibition, research and management centre it includes the Discovery Centre and related infrastructure along with a 280 parking spaces upgrade with benches, information signs, additional cycle racks, and improved links with public transport to allow for greater access to the reserve.⁴⁸

The centre is proposed as 'a forum for the resolution of nature conservation issues locally in the Nature Reserve and Dublin Bay, to promote the values of UNESCO and to inspire a sense of global citizenship to address global climate issues'.⁴⁹ This is an important remit.

However, if such a centre is necessary, it should not be located on the nature reserve for the following reasons.

EU Strategy: It disregards the EU's Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and runs counter to its statement that 'nature is in a state of crisis... we see the changes in our everyday lives' where buildings can be seen 'rising up on green spaces'.⁵⁰ This small and fragile nature reserve is already situated inside a city full of buildings and located beside two private golf clubs.

Gateway, Visitor Attraction & Habitat Fragmentation: The centre will act as a 'gateway' and visitor magnet to the reserve attracting 45,000 visitors in year one rising to 65,000 in year five according to the council.⁵¹ In addition to the this impact, a recent study also anticipates that the Bull Island reserve 'will continue to be impacted by increased footfall as the population and urbanisation of the city surrounds increases.'⁵²

As a result, the human encroachment and habitat fragmentation all of this generates will only intensify over time and further weaken this already depleted nature reserve. Habitat fragmentation has been found to reduce biodiversity by between 13% and 75% and its impact has been found to increase over time. Another study of 155 countries also found that visitor pressures elevates biodiversity risks and intensifies them in neighbouring areas.⁵³

This issue is particularly important in such a relatively small reserve as Bull Island which already bears the causeway road and roundabout fracture whose impact has grown over the years with the increasing numbers on the island. The Discovery Centre and the activity that it brings will be a significant new fracture, facilitating and enabling further pressures on the reserve.

Biosphere Reserve Pressures: The Dublin Bay Biosphere Reserve designation may add to this pressure. One study of biospheres found that 'protected areas can be drivers for urbanisation, as they may exert an attractive effect on urban development' mentioning that evidence from three biospheres in France, Spain and Portugal indicated the noticeable conversion of agricultural lands and natural areas to artificial surfaces in buffer zones due to urbanisation. It also noted that even the formerly remote areas of Ireland's western seaboard, including protected areas such as Kerry UNESCO Biosphere Reserve, are marketed as a day trip from Dublin to an 'unspoilt region' on tourism websites.

Another study refers to the lack of recognition for Biosphere Reserves within global conservation frameworks, partly because they are trying to do other things besides conservation

and a separate study considers the risks attached to Biosphere Reserves as tourism destinations.⁵⁴ The Dublin Bay Biosphere Reserve designation seems to provide less safety than its other designations.

Proposed Site Location: The council argues that the proposed location of the Discovery Centre off the Causeway Road is on reclaimed land. However, building on a protected site must pass a series of legal tests under the Habitats Directive where any project not necessary for the reserve's management must undergo an Appropriate Assessment as follows.⁵⁵

- a) The Precautionary Principle. Under EU law the project can only proceed if it can be proven beyond reasonable scientific doubt that it will not adversely affect the integrity of the reserve.
- b) The Integrity of Site test. The council must also prove that the activities around the centre's construction and the increasing visitor impact into the future will not harm Qualifying Interests (QI – protected habitats and species).
- c) In-Combination Effects: The proposal must also be considered in combination with the existing pressures on the reserve. Proving that a tipping point for these ecosystems will not be reached will be a significant challenge.

The EU's *Nature Restoration Law* (NRL) shifts the focus from merely 'protecting' what is there to 'restoring' what has been lost or degraded.⁵⁶ If the proposed location for the Discovery Centre were included in Ireland's National Restoration Plan as an area to be restored, then proposing this centre would clash with the law's restoration targets. Here the recent *Nature Restoration Report* advises that Ireland should restore nature on public lands as a priority and states that 'while the Irish State is a big landowner and is responsible for national obligations, up until now the actions for nature restoration have fallen heavily on private landowners'. In addition, it states that 'public lands can be utilised as places to demonstrate best practice in nature restoration and as sites on which to build the skills and expertise'.

It also states that local authorities are essential for creating the conditions for nature restoration and recommends that all habitats of county or city importance are mapped and that these are 'linked to corresponding protective policies and objectives'.⁵⁷

Dublin City Council could, of course, argue that there are important reasons for the centre's proposed location by stating that the research, education, exhibition, visitor 'gateway' elements of the proposal are of overriding importance.

However, the EU courts usually set a high bar for this, often requiring that there are no alternative locations for these functions. In particular, the research, education, exhibition and related visitor attraction functions on this small and fragile reserve are of no direct benefit to its wellbeing. The reserve's exposure to greater footfall, inspection, exploration, photo opportunity and everything else that follows such a centre will not benefit a single animal, plant or habitat.

Tender & Proposed Site Location: The Dublin City Council, Dublin Port and Fáilte Ireland steering committee tendered in November 2013 for qualified professionals 'to work with the steering committee to carry out a feasibility study ... for a ... new Interpretive Centre and

Visitor Experience at Bull Island.' The title of the tender and the details specify the Bull Island location. However, the architect's note on the feasibility study states that they considered five locations following which they recommended the causeway site. Therefore, the feasibility study recommended the Bull Island location as required by the original tender.⁵⁸

Under EU law project proposers should consider alternative locations as part of the environmental assessment process. This typically means fully documenting and justifying why a preferred location is chosen over others. The original tender clearly shows, however, that the decision was already made at the outset to locate the centre on the island rather than anywhere else.

The Department: The Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage expressed its concerns about the proposal stating that Bull Island and the protected habitats are already 'under severe threat from visitor movements and associated damage'.

It also states that even if an effective visitor and management plan were in place, the 'Department is not confident that if the provision of the Discovery Centre were to attract more visitors to Bull Island that there might not be increased adverse effects on QI habitats on the island as a result of higher human footfalls and possibly increased disturbance of QI or Special Conservation interest birds species for the North Bull Island SPA as well.'

Consequently, it requested the council to remove the Discovery Centre proposal from the Dublin City Climate Action Plan 2024-2029.⁵⁹

The Building & Tower: The centre will, according to the proposal, 'consists of a long, low horizontal form', with a lookout 'tower from which to view ... the full expanse of the bay' that is 'is inspired by the wide range of vertical structures' such as lighthouses, Martello towers, coastguard and folly towers.⁶⁰

The proposed tower does not appear to comply with the Planning and Development Act 2000 which states that 'a development plan shall include objectives for ... the preservation of the character of the landscape ... including the preservation of views and prospects and the amenities of places and features of natural beauty or interest'.⁶¹

Dublin City Council previously complied with this legislation when it was so attentive to the visual integrity and coherence of the island's landscape that a new roof on the replacement clubhouse for St Anne's Golf Club in 2003 had to be low-profile.⁶² Why then does the council not comply with this legislation today?

Carbon Impact & Circular Economy: The proposal involves the demolition of the Interpretative Centre built in 1986 (located off the roundabout at the top of the Causeway Road) and its replacement by the proposed Discovery Centre further down the Causeway Road.⁶³ However, best practices and modern science advises against a demolition and replacement strategy due its environmental impacts and proposes instead a 'retrofit-first' approach.

Retrofitting is favoured because it supports net zero construction goals and reduces embodied carbon. Embodied carbon in this situation is the Interpretative Centre's carbon footprint from birth and includes everything from manufacturing the materials to transporting them to site, the construction itself, and the energy used in demolition. This is the carbon cost we rarely see but

cannot ignore. Retrofitting supports the circular economy approach whereas demolition involves higher whole-life carbon emissions. Demolishing the 1986 Centre will release years of embedded carbon.⁶⁴

Even if the new building is more energy-efficient than a renewed Interpretative Centre, the large embodied carbon released by the demolition and new build will be substantial. Since the construction sector is the largest emitter of carbon, accounting for more than one-third of emissions, we must take all the opportunities we can to minimise its carbon footprint.⁶⁵

Dublin City Council's demolition and new build strategy on Bull Island disregards its own standards and the requirements it places on others. In its 're-use of existing buildings' standards it states that where a 'development proposal comprises of existing buildings on the site, applicants are encouraged to reuse and repurpose the buildings'.⁶⁶

It also contradicts its own advice to everyone else to work towards a circular economy which it defines as 'an economy that promotes efficient and low-carbon approaches' and reduces 'waste production and encourage the reuse of products and materials'. It also ignores the government circular economy plan and EU's work in the area.⁶⁷

The demolition and construction activity will bring significant pressures to the reserve and further impact its ecology and the proposed centre and tower will leave a large new structure on the island on a space that could have been restored to its natural state in support of EU's Biodiversity Strategy which asks us to be 'more ambitious on nature restoration'.⁶⁸

An Coimisiún Pleanála: To underpin this point, it is worth mentioning that An Coimisiún Pleanála, the state planning authority, recently refused planning permission for a development that required the demolition of an existing building because it would be contrary to the Dublin City Development Plan 'which seeks to promote and support the retrofitting and reuse of existing buildings'.⁶⁹

Cost: The estimated cost of the proposal in 2023 was €18.7m.⁷⁰ The Public Spending Code obliges public bodies 'to treat public funds with care' and ensure the 'best possible value for money'.⁷¹

Could this money be better spent elsewhere in view of the many difficulties attached to the proposal? Has Dublin City Council considered the opportunity cost of spending €18.7m of taxpayer's money on a Discovery Centre in such a problematic location over other pressing needs such as housing, homelessness, traffic congestion, flood defences, etc.

Opportunity cost is the foregone benefit of using this money elsewhere. If Dublin City Council has not considered the opportunity cost of its proposed €18.7m spend on a Discovery Centre in such an unsuitable location it indicates a failure in financial management and decision making.

One study found that policy makers were between 6% and 10% less likely to invest in a public spending program when reminded of opportunity cost. In addition, it found that public spending proposals and decisions by politicians adds to 'opportunity cost neglect in public policy'. Overall, the study found that the implications for not using opportunity cost in public spending is substantial causing misallocation of public money and leading to an artificially high demand for public spending.

The opportunity costs of public spending should be a required element of public spending debates and a greater use of techniques such as cost benefit and effectiveness analysis could be considered. This, according to the study, is rather rare at local level. Finally, the researchers found, 'to their surprise' that there was less opportunity cost neglect in consumer spending, especially among older people.⁷²

Another study discusses how the neglect of opportunity cost can also affect the proper functioning of democracy. When citizens overlook or are unaware of the trade-offs in a public spending proposal it has greater appeal than otherwise would be the case. This can also help to explain public overspend and weak finances at both national and local level. When, however, researchers and pollsters focus the public's attention on the sacrifices that any public spending decision has, support for it declines substantially.⁷³

Media Analysis: Opportunity cost is often overlooked in media analysis and reports. The blame-avoidance theory, for example, indicates that the media's focus on negative outcomes can pressurise decision makers to spend money to solve immediate problems without considering its alternative use. Here 'the avoidance of ... blame is crucial to understanding the behaviour of public officials'. When public servants 'fear being blamed for public service performance, spending more money for public services is a way to signal that they are actively doing something to improve performance and to consequently avoid blame in the future'.⁷⁴

Entry Fees: The council proposes that visitors are charged admission fees in line with OPW rates.⁷⁵ Will this cover the running costs of the centre? If not, will the centre be a continued burden on the taxpayer or will it need to generate extra revenue streams and more visitors?

Sea Levels: Dublin Bay has experienced higher rates of sea level rise than the global average and the factors affecting this are 'projected to continue and intensify into the future'. Although 0.95% of Ireland's total land area 'could be at risk of coastal flooding by 2050', the 'Dublin region is most at risk, with 2.41% of the total land area impacted'.⁷⁶ Why then is Dublin City Council proposing a Discovery Centre for a low lying sand spit in Dublin Bay?

When we add in the possibility of its exposure much sooner to more frequent, intense and damaging storms, the centre's proposed location, with everything else, becomes even more difficult to understand.

The extreme winds during Storm Darragh in December 2024 and Storm Éowyn in January 2025 could have had a larger impact on Dublin Bay had the concurrence of wind direction and other factors been different.⁷⁷

Coastal Protection: Concerns have been expressed about insuring properties near Bull Island where reports indicate that the major seafront flood defence scheme for the area is delayed in its design and planning phase.⁷⁸

The Environmental Protection Agency explains here that social acceptance issues 'have hampered adaptation in Clontarf' which is located opposite the southern end of Bull Island. The sea wall debate is seen as a 'failure in building consensus, leading to wasted resources and time in the preparation of plans, the construction and subsequent deconstruction of protective barriers, and the absence of sea walls that has followed'. This indicates that there are 'limits to

the capacity to deal with climate change and coastal flooding including finance and social acceptance problems'.⁷⁹

Why then is Dublin City Council trying to protect Clontarf from sea and storm damage when it proposes a new building on a low sandspit on the seaward side of this protection? If so will the Discovery Centre need its own sea wall protection?

Insurance for island location: In addition, will it be possible to insure the property in its proposed location? The Irish Central Bank requires insurers to incorporate climate change into their risk management and planning. At present, one in twenty buildings has limited access to flood cover and this is expected to increase with climate change. If the Central Bank had included coastal areas in its calculation it would greatly increase this estimate as coastal properties are more vulnerable to flooding.⁸⁰

Barrier Island: Bull Island is an important part of flood resilience and coastal protection in Dublin Bay. As a barrier-island complex of beach, dune and back-barrier lagoon it acts as the first line of defence, breaking the energy of storm surges before they reach the mainland. The back-barrier lagoon of tidal flats and salt marshes between the island and the shoreline also allows for the deposition of silt and growth of salt marshes, providing additional protection. In this context, it should be regarded as a dynamic part of the coastal defence system rather than a static piece of land to be built on.⁸¹

Congestion & Coastal Population: The proposed centre will increase traffic congestion in an already congested part of the city as indicated by the general literature on visitor attractions.⁸² Coastal populations are rising at three times the global average and this increase is particularly marked in urban areas like Dublin Bay.⁸³

Communications & Policy Coherence: The above leads us to ask do the different parts of Dublin City Council with their responsibilities for building standards, circular economy, coastal protection, flood relief, traffic management, climate change, and parks communicate effectively with one another?

There is a considerable management literature on such problems and more recently in dealing with climate and biodiversity. One source talks about 'persistent disconnects' and 'policy misalignment' that 'continue to constrain sustainable development and climate action' and the importance of starting on a better path by first recognising these problems.⁸⁴

The Debate

The debate on the proposed Discovery Centre has been ongoing for some time and discussion on the proposed location and related issues have appeared in the media over the years.⁸⁵ See Appendix 2.

The feasibility study was completed in 2014 and the centre was to have opened in 2017 and at a later stage in 2019. In October 2025, the city manager stated that the proposal 'will be lodged with An Bord Pleanála' without giving an indicative date. In April 2026 the city manager said 'I think there is still need to provide something' for the Discovery Centre in the council's 2026-2028 capital programme. A recent report by the *Dublin Inquirer* of the city councillors'

discussion on the capital programme referred to 'the credibility gap created by the council putting some projects in its capital programme again and again and not delivering them'.⁸⁶

Conclusion

Dublin City Council's Discovery Centre proposal ignores the spirit and details of the EU's strategy, law, and ambition, its government department's concerns, potentially significant visitor and construction and related habitat fragmentation impacts, its own carbon and circular economy rules and regulations and its coastal climate protection work. In addition, it seems to have ignored the use of opportunity cost methodology in its analysis of the project and indicates a lack of coherence and communication within its own organisation on the issue. For these and other reasons the council's proposed location for its Discovery Centre should be withdrawn.

If a Discovery Centre is necessary it should not be located on, or adjacent to, the nature reserve, should not be a gateway or magnet to the reserve, should focus on both biodiversity and climate resilience promotion and educational work, and should be a retrofit or refurbishment of an already extant building to comply with its own guidelines.

However, a new discovery centre in a city of over a million people creates a potentially congested and inequitable node for its residents. Dublin City Council should instead consider the possibilities of a *Distributed Learning Network* within key Dublin parks or other suitable locations to support the biodiversity and climate resilience awareness, dissemination, and promotion work of the city.

Rather than creating a single, standalone centre this would use public spaces, extant buildings, and other distributed resources to deliver a layered public engagement that is embedded throughout the city it interprets so as to strengthen and reinforce it as a living ecosystem and enhance its biodiversity and climate resilience over time. See Appendix 3.

The Interpretative Centre, for its part, should concentrate on managing the nature reserve and enhancing its biodiversity and climate resilience functions.

Dublin City Council through this process can become a model local authority on dealing with the biodiversity and related climate crisis everywhere.

Case Note: The Bull Island case can be classified as an *instrumental case* 'examined mainly to provide insight' into the biodiversity crisis by helping us to see more clearly the reality on the ground so we can better understand the crisis in general and how best to deal with it.⁸⁷

URBAN AREAS & BEYOND

Since green spaces are important for people's health, wellbeing, biodiversity and environmental resilience there should be nothing special about the Bull Island Nature Reserve.

Nature for Everyone

High-quality green space should be available to everyone and be an integrated part of every neighbourhood's local infrastructure. We should support and enhance nature reserves and protected areas because of the significant contributions they make to biodiversity and climate

resilience but we should also ensure that every community has its own accessible, high-quality green space.

Contemporary planning and research has moved towards distributed, local provision, while policy developments increasingly emphasise that everyone should have access to green space within walking distance. Concepts such as the '15-minute city' and urban greening reflect the move toward networked, neighbourhood-based provision rather than simply relying on standout sites like nature reserves. Biodiversity enhancement and related climate resilience solutions should be available everywhere.

The Irish planning guidelines recommends that 'opportunities to enhance the overall quantum of public open space' and 'restore and enhance nature and biodiversity within settlements is harnessed ... to protect certain habitats and biodiversity' and that 'ideally, all residents within a settlement will have access to a multi-functional public open space within walking distance of their home.'⁸⁸

The City & Urban Areas

Urban areas provide considerable opportunity for biodiversity enhancement. A review of 40 cities globally discussed a range of attributes for enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services to include in urban-planning, including goals for habitat conservation, air and water quality, ecosystem services and ecological connectivity and advised that such plans should be underpinned by quantitative targets.⁸⁹

Another source says that cities with rich and diverse urban nature can contribute to the protection of biodiversity and serve as important refuges for animals and plants. This discusses the importance of developing 'urban nature plans' that focus on biodiversity enhancement.⁹⁰ These plans should be integrated in the overall urban-planning process so as to ensure there are no inconsistencies, variances or silos within city authorities.

The EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 refers to area-based conservation and greening measures for cities and mentions the 11,000 Natura 2000 sites within, or partly within, cities representing 15% of the total area of the Natura 2000 network.⁹¹

Cities are also in focus because of increased heat and rainfall challenges.

Urban Heat Island Effect: Urban areas are getting hotter due to the urban heat island effect caused mainly by densely built and artificial surfaces such as brick, concrete and asphalt surfaces. Natural cover reduces the urban heat island effect through blocking or reducing the impact of solar radiation. In addition, vegetation and water bodies release water vapour which helps to cool the air and when brick, concrete, asphalt or similar surfaces are replaced or covered by soil, vegetation, and/or water bodies it further mitigates the heat impacts. Cities can, therefore, use nature-based solutions to reduce the urban heat island effect by expanding and enhancing green areas and cover everywhere in public, private and corporate spaces.

One study found that greenery on the ground (parks) and greenery on buildings (green roofs and green walls) typically reduce peak surface temperature by 2–9 °C and ~17 °C respectively while greenery on buildings also provides added thermal insulation for the building envelope. However, the cooling potential varies markedly, depending on the scale of operation, greenery extent, plant selection and placement. It concludes that urban planners must optimize design to

maximize mitigation benefits by, for example, interspersing parks throughout the city, allocating more trees than lawn space and using multiple strategies in areas where most cooling is required.⁹²

The urban heat island effect varies across countries and cities. The map below, for example, shows the variation in certain European cities.

Urban Heat Island intensity per city

Source: European Commission⁹³

Wetter Cities: Some cities are getting wetter. Ireland, for example, has become 7% wetter over the 1991–2020 period, with record rainfall in Dublin, including over 220% of the long-term average for January 2026 at two of its city weather sites. Recent research has also identified a significant shift in global precipitation dynamics, particularly since 2002, with an observed increase of approximately 1.8% in total precipitation. This is consistent with climate change projections indicating that global warming will intensify both the frequency and severity of extreme precipitation events.⁹⁴ Under the wetter city challenge we have various concepts and proposed solutions, one of which is the Sponge City.

Rain Management: We can classify the management of rain under three stages:

Direct rain – characterised by traditional infrastructure such as concrete pipes and gutters which are designed for immediate discharge of rainwater.

Combined Use – a transitional phase where cities began exploring the collection and use of rainwater for irrigation and industrial use.

System Management – a whole management approach to rain and water issues, such as, for example, Sponge City.

Urban Rain System Management – Sponge City

The Sponge City concept and practices aims to change urban infrastructures into green infrastructures to help absorb, regulate, and reuse precipitation, rehabilitate drainage systems, enhance water system connectivity, separate rainfall and sewage pipe networks, to improve the area's capacity to handle water issues.

As an urban rainwater management system the Sponge City uses blue–green infrastructure to restore natural water cycles through the accumulation, filtration, purification, storage, and reuse of rainwater while also delivering biodiversity and social benefits.⁹⁵

Sponge cities maintain, enhance or develop a variety of natural elements such as woods, lakes, ponds, wetlands, along with other green spaces such as roofs, borders, permeable pavements, and ecological waterfronts (land-water interface designed to function as a living ecosystem rather than just a paved urban edge). This system aims to increase water absorption and reduce water runoff so as to mitigate urban saturation. Second, it works to help improve water quality through self-purification systems and ecological waterfronts. Third, it aims to recycle stormwater for urban water supply by converting rainwater into a resource to address water shortages, especially during droughts.

Sketch of Sponge City⁹⁶

This system focuses on flooding and waterlogging from heavy rain which can cause property damage, interruptions in transit, and safety issues. Continuing urbanisation, industrialisation, and population growth are also causing water scarcity, pollution, heat island effects, soil erosion, ecological degradation, infrastructure overload, and public health concerns.⁹⁷

Interest in the sponge city concept and practice gathered pace after President Xi Jinping and the central Chinese government promoted it at its conference on December 12, 2013. Following this, in 2015 and 2016, the Chinese government selected 30 pilot cities for sponge city construction exploration based on their diverse natural and social conditions, and all of them completed performance assessments by the end of 2019.⁹⁸

The results from Shenzhen, for example, indicate that within the designated pilot zones, Sponge City interventions are associated with reduced surface runoff, reduced peak flows, and reported improvements in pollutant filtration, particularly where green infrastructure density and monitoring capacity are high. It also found that these results were uneven and impacted by governance constraints, including institutional fragmentation and maintenance capacity.⁹⁹

Sponge Planet

Kongjian Yu, regarded as the founder or main advocate of the Sponge City concept and practice, has recently written about the Sponge Planet. Here he refers to climate strategies that focus primarily on carbon and largely ignore the destabilised water cycle that amplifies disasters and accelerate climate change and proposes that slow water projects can help reverse

this trend. He also states that farming, forestry, grazing, mining and building have degraded 75% of land on Earth and have significantly altered the water cycle, which plays a key role in stabilising the climate.

Although water vapour is a greenhouse gas that can amplify the impact of excess carbon dioxide it is central to cooling the planet. He argues that our impact on the natural water cycle has been extreme where we have drained or filled as much as 87% of the world's wetlands and dammed and diverted 75% of the world's large rivers. Since 1992, human encroachment onto floodplains has paved an area the size of Ukraine. We need policies and funding that protect, restore, or mimic natural slow water systems, such as wetlands, floodplains, mountain meadows and forests.

The Sponge Planet model has three principles: 'absorb rain where it falls, restore water's natural slow phases, and adapt modern humans to accept more slow water on the land'. These principles are part of the Slow Water movement where 'projects protect and restore wetlands, floodplains, mountain meadows and forests, and mimic these natural systems with permeable surfaces'.

The article concludes by saying that 'decision makers or engineers will sometimes say that nature-based approaches are 'nice, but can't be a significant part of the solution'. That is a fundamental misunderstanding of scale. Because humans have degraded 75% of the land on Earth, thereby altering the water cycle, we need Slow Water projects distributed across watersheds, countries and continents, ultimately recreating a Sponge Planet'.¹⁰⁰

Distribution: A recent study of ecosystem services supply and demand across demographic and socioeconomic groups in Beijing and New York City found inequalities in green space distribution. In addition, not only was there a pattern of distributional differences within the city but more greenspace was added in areas with already high ecological supply, rather than high social demand or vulnerability.¹⁰¹

Reimagine the City & Urban Areas

We should reimagine the city and urban areas as high quality habitats and green and healthy places to live and work. Everything from nature reserves, parks, green spaces, hospitals, colleges, schools, businesses, charities, public organisations, streetscapes, homes, front and back gardens, streams, rivers, flat roofs, window sills and footpaths can all play a part.

There has been an increased interest in the literature in biodiversity within cities and urban areas. A recent review of the literature finds that 'despite biodiversity loss being more pronounced in cities, traditional conservation efforts ... are largely undertaken far from urban landscapes'. This review proposes 'urban rewilding ... to restore ecological functions and enhance ecosystem resilience' and suggests that it 'offers a promising approach to addressing the biodiversity crisis', especially in rapidly expanding cities.

In addition, it states that species reintroduction in urban landscapes can help restore absent or declining ecological functions, enhance ecosystem resilience, and reconnect urban populations with the natural world. Despite the challenges involved in making these changes it states that the potential benefits of urban rewilding are substantial and proposes that when undertaking species reintroductions close to people, these benefits can also include community engagement, and measurable health and well-being advantages to city dwellers.¹⁰²

Another review suggests that cities should become 'primary locations of climate activities' so as to create the climate-friendly cities of the future and points to a trend in the literature towards nature based solutions where climate benefits are supported by biodiversity resilience and improvements.¹⁰³ We now consider the international context.

INTERNATIONAL

The Bull Island Nature Reserve is a minute part of an interlocked system of habitats operating across the world. It is regionally connected to Irish and UK systems, internationally embedded in transcontinental marine and migratory networks and globally influenced by climate and ocean conditions. These habitats survive and endure by operating across borders and are dependent on each other for biodiversity and ecosystems services that cannot be confined inside the boundary of a single country.

Ecological connectivity is the 'unimpeded movement of species, connection of habitats without hindrance, and the flow of natural processes that sustain life on Earth.' It is important to maintain and restore this connectivity, in particular for priority habitats and species.

Connecting systems such as seas, lakes, rivers, wetlands, forests and mountain ranges cross national boundaries and, therefore, conservation or lack of it in one country can support or harm ecosystems in other countries.¹⁰⁴

Links

One of the best-known nature connections across the world is bird migration. Great Britain and Ireland are located along the East Atlantic Flyway. Their proximity to the major waterbird breeding areas in the Arctic, together with their mild climate and coastal and inland wetlands, make them important habitats for wildfowl and waders from autumn to early spring.

Waders: A flyway is the area travelled by a migratory bird over its annual cycle. Most species aim for the shortest possible route. Eight major flyways for waders are identified below.

Wader flyways of the world.¹⁰⁵

Summer Visitors: Migration pathways are also important for summer nesting birds. For example, the Cuckoo visits Bull Island to breed and lay its eggs in meadow pipits nests and travels the long distance to and from Africa to do so. The cuckoo's migration is a small part of the *Afro-Palearctic flyway* route for birds travelling between their breeding grounds in Europe

and Asia and wintering grounds in sub-Saharan Africa. This is the largest landbird migration network in the world, with an estimated 2.1 billion birds.¹⁰⁶

The British Trust for Ornithology (BTO) set up an important cuckoo migration tracking project in 2011.¹⁰⁷ The National Parks and Wildlife Service (NPWS) joined the project in 2023 with four tagged cuckoos adding an Irish dimension to the project.¹⁰⁸ The BTO map below shows the migration routes that the tagged Cuckoos travelled on to and from their breeding grounds.

Cuckoo Migration (BTO)¹⁰⁹

There are also a number of other uncommon nesting birds on Bull Island such as the Sedge Warbler and Wheatear who winter in western and southern Africa.¹¹⁰

These and other nesting birds such as Skylarks, Meadow Pipits, Stonechats, Linnets, and Reed Buntings are exposed to significant pressure from human disturbance during the breeding season.

Bioregions

A bioregion is a geographical area defined by the natural systems that sustain life within it. These regions reflect unique species pools with distinct origins, compositions, and evolutionary characteristics. They are shaped by geological and climatic barriers as well as historical and ecological factors. While a distinct unit, a bioregion is also significantly influenced by external processes and changing biodiversity patterns nearby and globally.¹¹¹ Below is a map of the world containing 185 discrete bioregions.¹¹²

Bioregions of the World¹¹³

The development and use of bioregions has also been said to reflect people's concern for biodiversity and its wellbeing and improvement.

Great Britain, Ireland & Faroe Islands Bioregion: This bioregion is part of the Anglo-Celtic Isles subrealm and contains five ecoregions: Celtic Broadleaf Forests, English Lowlands Beech Forests, North Atlantic Moist Mixed Forests, Caledon Conifer Forests and Faroe Islands Boreal Grasslands—totalling nearly 32 million hectares of land area.

Great Britain, Ireland & Faroe Islands Bioregion¹¹⁴

The Faroe Islands are a self-governing archipelago in the Kingdom of Denmark responsible for their own climate and biodiversity policies and outside the EU. They are involved in Nordic Cooperation which does collaborative work on a wide range of areas including biodiversity and climate and they share their Boreal Grassland ecosystem with others like Norway and Iceland but not with the rest of this bioregion.¹¹⁵

British & Irish Archipelago

Adomnán of Iona in the late seventh century referred to the British and Irish archipelago as the 'Islands of the Ocean', reflecting a worldview at the time that defined them by their relationship to the Atlantic.¹¹⁶ This perspective is important today.

Great Britain, the largest island in Europe, is approximately 3.5 times larger than Ireland. It is characterized by the rugged highlands and islands of Scotland in the north, the mountainous terrain of Wales in the west, and the rolling hills and plains of England in the south and east.

Ireland, the third-largest island in Europe, is shaped like a basin with a central lowland plain surrounded by a ring of coastal mountains and known for its rugged Atlantic coastline and many lakes.

Both islands have a temperate maritime climate though Ireland tends to be slightly cloudier and wetter due to it being the first stop for Atlantic weather systems.

The Great Britain and Ireland archipelago is a suitable unit for common and shared work on the biodiversity and the related climate crisis. However, there is no unit supporting the archipelago's joint engagement with their common biodiversity and climate crisis. This topic is discussed later.

EU

The Bull Island case can be placed in a wider European context by looking at trends in similar habitats. Here we find that protected dunes, grasslands, bog, mire and fen habitats in the EU have suffered worsening trends with over 50% of them showing a bad conservation status and

a strong prospect of further deterioration unless something significant is done. Within this grouping it is the coastal habitats like Bull Island that are 'predominantly affected by development' and that show the lowest proportion of assessments showing good conservation status.

However, these results most likely understate EU dune and coastal habitat deterioration as the condition in 63% of coastal and 50% of EU dune habitats are unknown. This means that the level of work needed to restore coastal and dune habitats is likely to be significant.¹¹⁷

The main causes of habitat deterioration across EU coastal regions are urban expansion and man-made structures like the proposed Bull Island Discovery Centre. These developments increase human activity and reflect a broader trend of coastline modification for commercial and recreational use.¹¹⁸

Solutions: The EU's *State of Nature* report indicates that the most common measure proposed for improving coastal and dune habitats is reducing the impact of outdoor and recreational activities. Key actions include restoring damaged areas, controlling visitor numbers, and increasing awareness.¹¹⁹

EU Ambition

The EU promises to be ambitious in reversing biodiversity loss and undertakes to lead by action and example to ensure the world's ecosystems are restored, resilient, and adequately protected by 2050. In addition, it proposes a specific focus on areas of high biodiversity or potential and states that these areas should be 'strictly protected' and, where possible, restored.¹²⁰ Can we meet this ambition?

CHALLENGE

Dealing with the Challenge

The term 'biodiversity' arises from the contraction of 'biological' and 'diversity'. It is a relatively new concept first emerging in 1985-6 and a somewhat complex one. One source defines it as the variety and variability of life on Earth. This reflects the standard scientific framework which separates biodiversity into: genetic diversity within a single species, species diversity and ecosystem diversity. Another sees it as the rich variety of living things that, woven together, support and sustain life on Earth. This emphasises the interconnectivity of nature. Here, biodiversity is more than a list of species, habitats and communities – it is a functional web of support. While the word biodiversity is relatively new, the study of biological variety has a long history going back to Darwin and beyond.¹²¹

Wicked Problems

Some writers categorise the biodiversity crisis as a 'wicked problem' characterised by urgency, uncertainty and complexity – the more we know about it 'the more difficult it becomes'.¹²²

Wicked problems are complex, contested, and difficult to solve. This concept originated in a 1973 paper by Ritter and Weber. They argued that many of society's problems are difficult to 'fix' because they are difficult to define, lack objective solutions and involve conflicting stakeholder values and perspectives

Wicked problems differ from science or engineering problems, which have agreed definitions and knowable solutions and where, for example, a new bridge will work or not. With a wicked problem, a solution is either 'better or worse,' not true or false, and each attempted 'solution' may change things rather than fully resolve the problem.

Science cannot solve wicked problems because of their nature. These problems often cannot be definitively described. For example, there is no such thing as an agreed public good and no objective definition of justice. Therefore, proposed solutions to such problems cannot be meaningfully correct or false and it makes no sense to talk about optimal solutions to such problems unless severe qualifications are first imposed.

Wicked problems are so called not because they are ethically bad but because they are challenging. However, Ritter and Weber suggested here that it is 'morally objectionable for the planner to treat a wicked problem as though it were a tame one.'¹²³

Wicked Actor Constellation: This argues that wicked problems should be understood as 'wicked actor constellations'.¹²⁴

If we take this approach we could, for example, argue that the biodiversity erosion on the Bull Island Nature Reserve is not caused by a 'bad actor' but by a wicked actor constellation such as the city authorities, general public, dog owners, golf clubs, transport and infrastructure companies, government, state agencies, and EU.

According to this approach, the various actors interact in ways that cumulatively degrade the reserve's biodiversity over time. Therefore, since responsibility is dispersed, enforcement fragmented, and competing mandates exist, ongoing biodiversity pressures continue without an identifiable culprit or someone who has enough power to resolve it.

The main difficulty with both the wicked problem and wicked constellation analysis is that their approach can leave us rather helpless in finding a way forward. This brings us to those who argue that wicked problems should be seen as problems of analysis.

Wicked Problems as Problems of Analysis: Wicked problems are complex problems with multiple layers and components that have to be understood and analysed by different disciplines and from different perspectives. This reality leaves us with evidence that is fragmented, incomplete, inconclusive, contested and without a common measure.

Therefore, we must develop an *analytical process* that helps us deal with this fact and start by recognising the knowledge challenge that we face in dealing with these problems.

Under this approach we have to combine science and knowledge with an integrative, adaptive and reflexive approach and with understanding, values and local context and we often find that *answers have to evolve as the problem unfolds and our understanding of it deepens*.¹²⁵ For example, it could be argued that the difficulties with the Discovery Centre proposal have become clearer over time as people have reflected on the issue.

In view of all of the above, how do the general public feel about biodiversity and the related climate resilience crisis?

Attitudes to Biodiversity

Research indicates that there has been an increase in the recognition and understanding of biodiversity in the EU. Here, 71% say they have heard of the term, 41% say they know what it means and 66% see nature as essential to tackling climate change.

In addition, 45% of Europeans say that economic development that damages nature in protected areas should be prohibited while another 45% feel the damage is only acceptable for major public projects and if it is fully compensated for. Only 6% feel economic development should take precedence over biodiversity.¹²⁶

This looks helpful. However, what is the relative support for biodiversity?

Here, a recent Eurobarometer survey finds the environment and climate change is now the most important concern of EU citizens followed by rising prices, immigration, the economy, and health. But there is no direct mention of nature or biodiversity indicating that biodiversity is not yet a significant public issue among the general public.¹²⁷

Therefore, we need to find ways to make the biodiversity crisis clear, present and urgent to everyone. How might this happen? Let us consider Toynbee.

Challenge and Response

Toynbee's 12 volume study of history indicates that civilizations rise and fall based on how effectively they respond to the challenges they face.

Although he regarded challenges to be a fundamental threat to society he did not see them purely in negative terms. This is because he felt they carried within them the seeds of success. Toynbee's study deals with the growth and genesis of civilizations and argues that the proper field of study is the civilization and not the nation.

It is worth mentioning that Toynbee's work was motivated by the impact of WW1. He said it was 'not until August 1914 ... that I became aware of the practical reason for studying history comprehensively... In 1915 and 1916, about half the number of my school fellows were killed ... Thucydides in August 1914 had given me a shock that I am feeling still ... The writing of this book has been one of my responses to the challenge that has been presented to me by the senseless criminality of human affairs.'¹²⁸

Today, we might talk about Western or Eastern civilisation's fight against the biodiversity and climate crisis. However, we are just one world and one civilization in this fight. Nature sees no boundary.

We must, therefore, be aware of the role and responsibilities of individual nations. These units of our world are important components of action, practices, leadership and encouragement, and countries that slow or weaken the world's response are their own best enemy and everyone else's weak link.

However, it is not just nations that count. Inside each country its regions, communities, neighbourhoods, families, and individuals can make a contribution and influence developments.

A recent study indicates the importance of individual autonomy for our wellbeing. This suggests that having autonomy significantly enriches our life and can, to some extent, compensate for poorer basic life conditions in shaping our subjective well-being. One study

found that poor autonomy at work and home noticeably increased the risk of certain illnesses, such as depression and heart diseases.¹²⁹

So, on the basis of this analysis, people who feel involved and helpful in the face of the biodiversity challenge will, on balance, have a better level of life satisfaction.

Following on from this, how can we improve people's knowledge of, and interest in, biodiversity? How can we encourage change?

Factors Encouraging Change

Human behaviour drives all the main threats to biodiversity. Of the many species around the world under threat, 98% are threatened exclusively by processes driven by human behaviour.¹³⁰ Therefore, influencing our knowledge, interest and behaviour is critical. So, how can human behaviour change?

Nature Connectedness: Nature is important for our wellbeing, as we saw earlier. However, it is also important for our ability to deal with the crisis. Nature connectedness can be defined as the psychological relationship we have with nature, how we feel part of it, and care about it, and refers to the extent to which we regard nature as part of our identity.

This works in both directions. Nature is important to us, our society and our economy and when we feel connected to it we in turn want to protect it. According to a recent study 'nature connectedness is increasingly recognised as a causal issue in environmental crises and a powerful strategy for transformative change'. When people are less connected to nature, government plans and targets become more fragile and less welcome than if there is a greater society wide connectedness to nature. Therefore, we should enhance nature connectedness 'at the scale and pace necessitated by the global crises'.¹³¹

Direct Experience: Change can happen through encounters with nature. Research indicates that experiences of nature tend to increase the likelihood of being in favour of caring for it. Despite the decline in childhood experiences in our more urbanised society increased experiences of nature can help promote positive attitudes to biodiversity improvements.¹³²

Local Nature Areas: People everywhere should have their own nature area where they can walk and enjoy themselves among trees, rivers and streams, wild hedgerows and green spaces. There should be nothing special about places like Bull Island. Nature access should be available everywhere and for everyone. See Appendix 4.

Visiting Nature: Finding suitable nature places to visit is sometimes not that easy, especially when we are in an unfamiliar location. The *Wildling app* provides a large number of recommended locations in the UK along with information and maps on different locations. On release in 2025 it provided a directory of over 1,500 nature spots throughout Great Britain and Northern Ireland, from woodlands and coastlines to city parks and reserves, with 60 in Northern Ireland. Each location has photos, descriptions, maps, and filters based on preferences such as family-friendly, children, and walking factors. It also provides a content hub with practical ideas for activities such as building dens and rock pooling and allows users to create, save, and share nature spots with others.¹³³

Medical and Health Sectors: A recent study suggests that nature prescribing is a useful addition to conventional health care for improving peoples' health and wellbeing.¹³⁴ If nature prescribing expands it should lead to an increase in nature visits.

Education and Training: Research indicates that learning about biodiversity in primary and secondary school can influence knowledge and attitudes on conservation.¹³⁵ Research also indicates the benefits of getting out of the classroom and into nature for certain types of learning.¹³⁶

Improving the knowledge and skills of the workforce to enable staff to deal more effectively with the biodiversity emergency is important.¹³⁷ In addition, public servants will require new knowledge, training and skill enhancement supports to more effectively deal with the policy, legislative and administrative changes that will arise.

A recent study states here that policy growth leads to an accumulation of burdens for those implementing the policies and that administrative capacities need to keep pace with ever-growing implementation burdens.¹³⁸ Another study talks about the importance of professionally trained and rule-bound civil servants providing a potent tool for dealing with turbulent times.¹³⁹

A European Commission technical support project also refers to the importance of 'awareness raising, capacity building and training of authorities in charge of nature and biodiversity as well as in other relevant areas'.¹⁴⁰

Climate Resilience: Biodiversity improvements can make a significant contribution to the battle against climate change and this contribution should be actively encouraged and effectively coordinated. Examples of biodiversity policy in action to strengthen climate resilience and adaptation across Europe can be found in the latest *European State of the Climate 2025* report.¹⁴¹ See also Appendix 5.

Conservation Organisations: Conservation groups are important. For example, Birdwatch Ireland, RSPB and the BTO all do good work in protecting birds and their habitats.¹⁴²

Construction Sector: The construction sector should integrate biodiversity into its work as it continues to grow apace. The global construction sector is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of about 4.0% between 2025 and 2033. Ireland's construction sector is expected to grow by 4.8% on average from 2026-2029.¹⁴³ We should consider the possibility of integrating Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) into Irish legislation. Introduced in England in 2021 it mandates developers to ensure that a development leaves the natural environment in a measurably better state than before, increasing biodiversity by at least 10%.¹⁴⁴

Media: The media has an important role to play in conservation and some argue that it needs to give greater attention to biodiversity and more prominence to linking it with climate change. The BBC's Natural History Unit, its Springwatch and Autumnwatch series and David Attenborough and his colleagues' work over the years have been helpful in this respect.¹⁴⁵

Events: Some events are so significant that they can result in substantial change. The COVID-19 pandemic, for example, led to substantial changes in normal living. Researchers have

studied how agenda-setting can be influenced by events and how they can bring about change.¹⁴⁶

However, not making the necessary changes until some major biodiversity event happens is unwise. Is there something else we need to know and following that is there something else we can do?

In this context, we look at what Ireland has been doing at national level on the crisis.

IRELAND

Ireland's parliament, Dáil Éireann, declared a biodiversity and climate emergency in 2019. Following this, the government established a Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity in February 2022 to examine and advise on how to improve the state's response to the biodiversity crisis.

Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity

The assembly, including 99 randomly selected members of the public and an independent chairperson published its report and recommendations in March 2023. This included 159 recommendations on biodiversity loss of which there were 73 high-level recommendations and 86 sectoral-specific ones.

All its public meetings were live streamed and archived online and the papers presented to its members were made available online. This indicated a notable level of transparency in contrast to public bodies who have been criticised for their lack of openness and was regarded as one of the important elements of its success by commentators. One writer at the time hoped it might help break the deadlock in responding to the biodiversity crisis by offering 'political cover' for the necessary changes.¹⁴⁷

Oireachtas Report: The Dáil referred the Assembly's report to the Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action in June 2023. The Joint Committee, in turn, published its report that December and focussed on those recommendations where it felt there were gaps in implementation.¹⁴⁸

Outcome: The Citizens' Assembly did good work and the Joint Committee noted many of the early changes that followed. However, in spite of this it did not create the level of public engagement, interest and buy-in necessary for the quantum of change that is required to deal with the biodiversity emergency.

Citizens' assemblies have faced a number of questions. Some writers have looked at ways of improving the representativeness of the citizens' panels¹⁴⁹ Others have discussed issues around the steering or framing of the agenda and the creation of consent through the carefully framed structures which operate. Others have cast doubts on whether these assemblies are truly conducive to new policy and buy in by the general public and the loss of impetus over time in following through on the recommendations.¹⁵⁰

National Plan: Ireland's 4th National Biodiversity Action Plan 2023–2030, published in January 2024, focuses on reversing biodiversity decline through a 'whole of government, whole of society' approach, backed by new legislation.¹⁵¹ It has been referred to as Ireland's 'most ambitious biodiversity agenda to date' and is the first backed by legally binding targets.¹⁵²

The World Wildlife Fund (WWF) states it is an improvement on previous plans and notes that its objectives are complemented by targets with clear actions and indicators of success and that it has been placed on a statutory footing making implementation of actions a legal obligation while also indicating some weaknesses with the plan.¹⁵³

Question: On the above basis, Ireland has made important changes in its efforts to deal with the biodiversity crisis.

Why then does 90% of its protected habitats have an unfavourable status, up from its previous record of 85%?

And why, in the face of the evidence against it, is the Discovery Centre proposal still around? Is there something else going on – something relating to the general difficulty of dealing with this crisis? And following this, is there something else we can do to more effectively deal with the challenge?

OECD

The OECD emphasises the need for effective policy integration when dealing with the biodiversity, climate and related challenges and recommends a more coherent response to the interconnected nature of these challenges.¹⁵⁴

In addition, a recent OECD study states that government and local authorities in Ireland still operate within traditional 'silos' of responsibility which needs to change to meet the challenges faced. Here it states that Ireland often fails to translate its ambitious plans into successful outcomes and advises that policy coherence between national and local level should be made a strategic priority because the fragmentation between national and local level is one of the key challenges it faces.¹⁵⁵

Therefore, despite its ambitious and highly regarded actions at national level, the crisis remains. How can Ireland more effectively respond?

RESPONSE

The biodiversity crisis needs a more fundamental response. One that builds on the work to date and facilitates a society wide focus on change.

National Forum

Ireland moved from being a poor and underdeveloped society on its independence to becoming an advanced mixed economy.¹⁵⁶ Probably one of its greatest achievements was its work with others over the years in helping to bring about peace in Northern Ireland. A critically important part of the ground work for this was the New Ireland Forum in 1983-84.

New Ireland Forum

The New Ireland Forum was built around an influential all-party group to explore how lasting peace and stability could be achieved on the island of Ireland through the democratic process and to report on structures and processes through which this might be achieved.¹⁵⁷ Set up against a background of deep divisions, insecurity and violence at the time it was a landmark

consultative body established to find a constitutional path to ending the Northern Ireland conflict.

Composed of the four main constitutional nationalist parties on the island, its 27 members were elected politicians and included the leaders of the four parties and Taoiseach. The chairman was an academic and submissions were made by academics, business leaders, religious figures, and ordinary citizens, but only the politicians could vote and debate the final report. The first session was held in public in Dublin Castle on 30 May 1983 and its report was published on the 2 May 1984.¹⁵⁸

The Forum met almost 100 times in public and private sessions and in steering committee deliberations. It considered over 300 submissions, consulted with British political parties and every responsive Northern Ireland party. It operated in the form of a conference or forum, published a variety of important papers on different topics, received a significant amount of media attention and its public sessions were televised on RTE (Ireland's National Television and Radio Broadcaster).

Regarded at the time as a 'truly significant development' representing 'a profound change of mind and attitude', it had a significant impact on public opinion and research indicated an 'exceptionally high' level of awareness among people of its work at 96%. This interest was maintained across all demographic groups with, for example, the 18-24 and 25-34 age groups scoring 93% and 96% respectively. In addition, 53% found it a useful exercise at the time rising to 62% among the middle class. Awareness among people in Northern Ireland was also very high at 88%.¹⁵⁹

The forum had a powerful long term impact and is regarded as a 'visionary event' marking a turning point from a strong unification instinct in the Republic to a consensus based approach. The forum is seen as central to the evolution of public opinion and 'helped begin (the) process of changing hearts and minds' and indicated, according to some, that 'every major political breakthrough requires significant imagination and courage'. One source reflecting back on its work over 30 years later concluded that in the end it turned out to be 'a transformative education process ... for all of Ireland'.¹⁶⁰

System-Wide Change: According to one study, system-wide crises are hard to solve because of such factors as fragmented institutions and competing interests, entrenched narratives, confidence-sapping histories of failure, and the influence of multiple and overlapping fields. Change, however, becomes possible when a crisis is reframed in ways that enable cooperation and collective action on a way forward.

This study states that the New Ireland Forum helped establish a 'platform for new thinking' and created 'a new narrative' fundamental in moving to a rational and solutions based approach to the challenge of peace in Northern Ireland. This new narrative allowed for the mobilization of cooperation and collective action towards the reduction of violence and the movement towards peace.

Here it argues that reframing the narrative opens up the possibilities of system-wide changes where lack of change 'had been a long legacy feature'. Most interestingly it refers to the importance of changing the narrative when facing complexity and a diverse network of actors all of which is relevant to the biodiversity and related climate challenges we face.¹⁶¹

The impact of the Citizen's Assembly on Biodiversity pales in comparison to the impact of the New Ireland Forum. The Assembly did not have a transformative impact on society. No equivalent structure in modern Ireland has matched the forum's educational, reframing and narrative impact.

National Forum on Biodiversity & Climate Resilience

A well planned National Forum on Biodiversity and Climate Resilience would inject a considerable society wide focus on the crisis. Operating in a different time and context it faces a less visceral but in some ways more dangerous challenge and will be greatly assisted by the fact that Ireland is part of a global crisis with a developed science and best practice base, an engaged EU, and an international focus on dealing with the issue.

Our understanding of biodiversity loss and our capacity to deal with it has improved over the years. The percentage of studies reporting positive ecological outcomes has increased significantly. For example, more than half of the studies initiated between 2000 and 2009 reported positive ecological outcomes and this rose to 61% for those starting between 2010 and 2019. Another study finds that in two-thirds of cases, conservation either improved the state of biodiversity or slowed declines. Specifically, interventions targeted at species and ecosystems, such as invasive species control, habitat loss reduction and restoration, protected areas, and sustainable management were found to be highly effective. These findings provide important evidence that conservation actions have become increasingly effective.¹⁶²

In spite of this, there is significant evidence of helplessness among people about our capacity to deal with both the biodiversity and climate challenge. For example, a major survey of 10,000 children and young people reveals the emotional toll of climate and environmental threats with many saying their anxiety affects their daily functioning. Here, dissatisfaction with government responses was found to be widespread among young people and this dissatisfaction was associated with a perceived failure by governments to adequately respond to the crisis. So, in spite of the improvements in our knowledge and technical capacity to deal with the biodiversity emergency, many are distressed by the fact that we are not dealing adequately with the challenge and are burdened by a sense of helplessness.¹⁶³

This leads us to the important question of how do we better enable our society to more effectively tackle the biodiversity emergency? Here, we need to better connect the scientific, political and administrative worlds with the wider society so as to provide a firmer base for effective solutions to be better understood, supported and embedded in our society.

Previously, the 1983-84 New Ireland Forum did just that by helping to provide the society wide understanding necessary at the time to shift the national consciousness on the Northern Ireland issue.¹⁶⁴

The biodiversity and related climate emergency today is more urgent than the Northern Ireland crisis was in the eighties. In addition, the scientific, administration and political basis for a national forum on biodiversity is more highly developed today.

Configuring and developing it will require an effective formulation of its rationale, focus, schedule of activities and expected outcomes. Society's understanding of, and engagement

with, the biodiversity reality is an essential ingredient in dealing with the crisis and this is something a well-planned forum or equivalent could develop and encourage.

To deal with the crisis, we must understand it more fully. This knowledge will help us look beyond our small quarrels and realise that in the movements of the natural world there are great forces steadily bearing down on all of us.¹⁶⁵ A well organised forum could help tackle the crisis step by step and more rapidly and effectively than we have done to date.

The biodiversity crisis is a shared crisis. We experience it together in our community, region and country. We also share it with our close neighbours, in our local bioregion, wider regional context, continent, and across the planet and it is that we operate together in dealing with this common challenge.

International Context

There is a growing discussion on cross country collaboration in biodiversity, climate and environmental cooperation. A recent study of the literature on transnational cooperation advises countries to collaborate on these problems and harvest the synergies involved.

It also notes the 'strong link between biodiversity and climate adaptation' and 'nature based solutions', reflecting a new paradigm that sees environmental problems as interconnected systemic problems rather than single issues to be tackled and advises that we move beyond 'mere regulation' to creating adaptive and solid systems.¹⁶⁶

Transnational & Transboundary Conservation

We consider both transnational and transboundary conservation.

Transnational Conservation is conservation that operates across countries. It involves conservation cooperation, governance coordination, and institutional linkages operating across national boundaries. This can involve transnational agreements, networks, contracts and operate as a coalition of states, corporations, NGOs, or civil society actors working on conservation goals across countries.¹⁶⁷

Transboundary Conservation, by contrast, refers to conservation cooperation across borders. A transboundary area is a clearly defined geographical space that straddles one or more international boundaries and includes land, water and marine areas.

This involves coordinated or shared actions such as planning, management, data exchange, and policy alignment to protect species and habitats that cross borders. This is important because unilateral conservation efforts often fail to maintain connectivity and resilience across borders. There are more than 200 examples of transboundary cooperation, ranging from informal agreements to government-to-government treaties. The Fertő-Hanság National Parks in Austria and Hungary is an example, with its research and monitoring elements, transboundary tourism products, and promotion of the local cultural heritage. Similarly, the trilateral Dauria International Protected Area shared by China, Mongolia and Russia benefits from joint projects involving 200 monitoring stations in the study of species and habitats.

A transboundary conservation zone requires planning, governance framework, shared vision, clear definition of processes, roles and responsibilities, and mutually agreed management and monitoring guidelines.

Transnational conservation can be regarded as a broader category of cross-country conservation governance, within which transboundary conservation—focused on border-straddling ecosystems—can be considered a subset.

An important element of a transnational conservation is joint monitoring and evaluation. This facilitates scale economies through pooling expertise, infrastructure, and funding, creating 'opportunities for capacity building', avoiding duplication and 'accelerating the development and adoption of innovative methodologies'.

Benefits of international cooperation: Improved survival rates for migratory species who occupy better breeding, feeding and resting habitats. In addition, it also brings benefits from sharing heavy equipment, enforcement, best practices, monitoring and patrols, restoration work, preparation of educational material, exchanges and capacity building programmes along with economic, socio-cultural and good relations benefits.¹⁶⁸

We now look at the British-Irish Council (BIC).

British-Irish Council

The BIC is an intergovernmental organisation established under the Good Friday Agreement to promote positive, practical relations on an East-West basis between the people of the UK and Ireland. It operates through its eight administrations or governments (UK, Ireland, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales, Isle of Man, Jersey, and Guernsey).

Meeting twice annually at summit level and about three to four times a year at ministerial level it organises its work around three main thematic areas – climate and decarbonisation, culture and heritage, and economic and social inclusion.

Under the climate and decarbonisation theme it cooperates on shared environmental and climate challenges and includes work on energy, transport, housing, decarbonising economies and protecting the natural environment. This aims to accelerate the transition to net-zero emissions, share best practice on energy and housing policy, and align approaches to climate adaptation.

The eleven works sectors bring together officials and ministers from the member administrations to share best practice and collaborate on an ongoing basis on specific areas of cooperation and information-sharing.¹⁶⁹

British-Irish Council Administrations

The environment work sector, for example, was established in 1999 to share environmental expertise and learning across the member administrations. The environment Ministerial meeting in May 2025 established an invasive species work sector and agreed that the circular economy would be an important area of focus.¹⁷⁰

The planning and places work sector, established in 2009, facilitates knowledge sharing on spatial planning, urban/rural development, and infrastructure projects. It focuses on sharing best practices, addressing common challenges, and improving policy development. The November 2024 meeting stated that the 2025-27 plan would have two themes: climate change and the biodiversity emergency and skills and capacity for the public sector planning profession.

Climate and Biodiversity: Here the Planning and Places work sector identifies key challenges and shares best practice examples in planning responses. Among the areas of investigation are managing flood risk; the loss, promotion and enhancement of biodiversity; and the delivery of greater carbon efficiency in new development.

Skills and capacity: It also investigates how to make planning a more attractive profession and build capacity in the planning profession. The meeting's communiqué notes the challenge faced in attracting and retaining public sector planning staff at a time when many planners face increasing workloads and changing policy contexts, especially relating to biodiversity and nature issues.¹⁷¹

The secretariat, based in Edinburgh, is hosted by the Scottish Government and has six full-time staff on assignment from the membership administrations.

BIC decisions are made by consensus and individual members can opt-out of participating in specific common areas or actions.

Sometimes seen as the talking shop of the Good Friday institutions it was originally included because of unionists fears of an imbalance in the institutions and because it reflected John Hume's hope of strengthening the totality of relations between the islands. Hume, one of the principal architects of the Agreement, shared the Nobel Peace Prize with David Trimble in 1998. In recent times, it has been quietly doing good work, building relations and exchanging best practices among the member administrations.¹⁷²

On cross-border research on the island of Ireland, the Co-Centre for Climate + Biodiversity + Water was initiated through a joint effort by the governments of Ireland and the UK, following through on several high-level political commitments on the area. The funding base for the project was launched as part of a wider "Co-Centres" programme in October 2022 by ministers representing Ireland, the UK and Northern Ireland. While the funding was initiated by the governments, the centre's specific structure and research goals emerged from existing academic partnerships.¹⁷³

Nordic Council of Ministers

A comparative but more powerful cross country structure is the Nordic Council of Ministers (NCM) between Norway, Sweden, Finland, Iceland, and Denmark which was set up in 1971. This has long-standing cooperation on climate adaptation, biodiversity, and marine

protection, joint research programmes, shared datasets, and coordinated policy advice and respects full national sovereignty while delivering practical alignment.¹⁷⁴

The NCM focuses on coordinating policies in areas like environment, education, culture, labour, and health and sustainability with biodiversity and climate being part of its work.

UK

The UK faces a similar biodiversity crisis to that in Ireland. Although there have been some important developments along with successes for certain species, the main trend over the years has been one of continued decline to when in 2023 the *State of Nature* report classified it as one of the most nature-depleted countries in the world.

Since 1970, the abundance of monitored wildlife species in the UK has fallen by an average of 19% and about 16% of species are threatened with extinction in Great Britain. This risk is even higher for specific groups like birds at 43% and terrestrial mammals at 26%.

Only a small fraction of the UK's most important habitats are in favourable condition with, for example, only 7% of woodlands and 25% of peatlands in a good ecological state. In addition, the distribution of bees, hoverflies, and moths has decreased by roughly 18% on average.

The UK has set ambitious targets to address the crisis and the *State of Nature* reports states that although it has the expertise to do the job adequate resources are needed to support the necessary changes.¹⁷⁵

Although the long-term data above are stark, the more recent short-term trends show a plateauing for some species and a 'glimmer of hope'. The UK is no longer losing species at the same rapid speed that was seen during the peak of industrial farming. However, it remains today a nature-depleted country similar to Ireland.¹⁷⁶

The members of the Great Britain and Ireland archipelago share a common biodiversity crisis and should, in the face of this common challenge, take a more connected approach to the crisis. The archipelago shares seas, weather systems, migration routes, similar ecosystems, landscapes, etc. Both face the same biodiversity and climate crisis. Addressing them more effectively will require a more cohesive approach to this common crisis.

UK–Ireland Biodiversity & Climate Resilience Unit

The UK and Ireland should consider establishing a joint Biodiversity & Climate Resilience Unit to support biodiversity improvement and related climate resilience across the archipelago through monitoring of relevant developments, identifying and disseminating best practices, and supporting capacity building in the area.

This would be a focused, permanent and science-led unit that:

1. Develops a *shared intelligence system* with common biodiversity and climate resilience indicators, data, early warning and long-term monitoring systems so as to monitor and assess shared biodiversity and related climate risks across the archipelago's ecosystems on an ongoing basis. This system should be aligned with best international standards
2. Identifies and disseminates *best practices* to facilitate a better understanding of what works and thereby encourage and support the development and implementation of more effective policies and actions across the archipelago.

3. Prevents duplication, improves efficiency and reduces biodiversity and related climate risks across the archipelago.

Development Stages

The unit could be developed as follows.

- a) *Consideration Stage*: Both governments consider the idea using international best practices, the British-Irish Council's experience, and UK-Ireland intergovernmental cooperation.
- b) *Pilot Development*: Develop the pilot and clarify its work areas and remit. (6 months)
- c) *Pilot Stage*: Pilot and review the unit's operation. (1-2 year) with 2-3 flagship programmes. Test the shared intelligence system.
- d) *Establishment Stage*: Establish the unit as fully operational with long-term funding and resources in place. Review and develop the unit over time as necessary.

Elements

Management: The unit could, for example, come under a suitable biodiversity and climate resilience ministerial council under the British-Irish Council which would enhance its role in strengthening relations between the islands by fortifying resilience, reducing risk, and delivering better outcomes across the archipelago. In this way it becomes a technical unit for the benefit of all member administrations with a standing work programme and a permanent technical secretariat or office.

Scientific Board: A scientific board to advise the ministerial council and secretariat.

Secretariat Resources: 20-30 fully resourced staff during the 1-2 year pilot stage along 80-100 fully resourced staff when established. Note these staff may be part of a full-time seconded basis for a medium term 3 year period in order to bring in additional skills, experience or knowledge at an early stage.

Operations: Monitoring biodiversity and related climate resilience changes and analysing, identifying, and disseminating best practices so as to strengthen biodiversity and related climate resilience, reduce risks and enhance efficiency.

Funding: Core funding provided by UK-Ireland governments and administrations on an agreed basis.

Supplementary funding: EU to carry out additional work.

Contrast with NCM

The proposed UK–Ireland unit is a monitoring, risk management, knowledge enhancement and evidence base unit. The Nordic model, by contrast, is defined by history and identity whereas the UK-Ireland unit would be defined by factors such as common location, weather systems, biodiversity, climate, seas, and challenges. Its pace would be responsive, active, future focused in order to reduce biodiversity and climate risks and support the common knowledge, data and best practices base necessary for more effective actions in the neighbouring jurisdictions and archipelago.

As a focused and science led operation it would concentrate on data integration, risk assessment, early warning, best practices identification and dissemination, and while being proactive, support information gathering and decision making in real time.

Relatively lighter and more agile than the Nordic model, its secretariat would have a minimal governance overhead and clear reporting lines to existing departments, important when dealing with fast-moving nature and climate risks. This is a support unit, not an integrative one, by contrast the Nordic Council of Ministers is a regional cooperation project embedded in a wider Nordic identity.

DISCUSSION

Travelling up into the sky we eventually reach the Earth's limb, the edge of the world before we head out into space. The biodiversity and climate crisis can be seen even from space with visible signs of deforestation, habitat changes, coral bleaching, wildfires, desertification, melting ice, and shrinking wetlands.¹⁷⁷

This report looks at the biodiversity and related climate resilience crisis through the lens of a small country in the North Atlantic. The introduction briefly outlines the importance of nature to everyone and the trends in biodiversity internationally, in protected areas around the world, in the EU, and in Ireland.

To help ground the discussion the report considers the case of Dublin's Bull Island Nature Reserve, Ireland's most designated site, the problems it faces, and the possibility that with a renewed vision it can become a model for urban biodiversity and climate resilience everywhere. Here it proposes a Distributed Learning Network across the city for biodiversity and climate resilience awareness, promotion, and support rather than the proposed Discovery Centre by Dublin City Council. In doing so, it reimagines cities everywhere as high quality habitats, climate resilient spaces and healthier places to live. In addition, it proposes that everyone should have access to high-quality green spaces which should be regarded as a normal part of every neighbourhood's infrastructure.

Following this it discusses the international context, ecological connectivity, international migratory links and bioregions. It then looks at the Great Britain, Ireland and Faroe Islands Bioregion and the British and Irish archipelago after which it considers EU developments in biodiversity and the EU's ambition on biodiversity improvement.

It then discusses the challenge and how to deal with it by considering the biodiversity crisis as a wicked problem, people's attitude to biodiversity, a historian's view on dealing with huge society wide challenges, factors encouraging change, and some of the things we can do about the problem.

It then outlines Ireland's response to the biodiversity challenge at national level and finds that despite these developments the situation on the ground has still not significantly improved and in some cases the trends continue to go in the wrong direction and following that discusses the OECD's advice on how Ireland could more effectively respond to the crisis.

The response section of the report suggests an additional proposal at national level and one at cross country level. At national level, we go back in time to the Northern Ireland Troubles, the

period of conflict, violence and terrorism which ran from the late 1960's to the Good Friday Agreement in 1998. Here we discuss the role of the New Ireland Forum (1983–84) in helping to facilitate the development of a new understanding, a new path forward in what was then a period of significant crisis.

Based on its success at the time the report proposes that a National Forum on Biodiversity and Climate Resilience at national level be considered and that this would be a significant improvement on the Citizens' Assembly model, joint parliamentary committees, and national plans.

Second, the growing focus on cross country collaboration, transnational and transboundary conservation, reflects the weakness of national plans on biodiversity and climate resilience. With no borders in the natural world, standalone national actions can lead to inefficiencies, duplication, resilience and risk issues due to inadequate cross border and cross country coordination and actions.

Here it considers the work of the British-Irish Council which plays a relatively limited role in the common crisis faced across the archipelago and also the Nordic Council of Ministers, a more powerful and longer standing form of cooperation.

Having looked briefly at how some of the UK data on biodiversity indicate similar challenges to Ireland, the report proposes a UK–Ireland Biodiversity and Climate Resilience Unit that would build on the work over the years between the UK and Ireland.

Both of these mechanisms will require detailed cooperation and planning between the parties involved.

Cooperation & Trust: The literature indicates that crises are more easily weathered if trust levels and other aspects of the social and institutional fabric are sufficiently high and well-maintained when a crisis hits. At an individual level, happy people are more likely to collaborate and cooperate during negotiations and happiness has been shown to enhance curiosity and creativity as such people are more likely to feel energetic and interested in doing things.

For Aristotle, humans are social animals, with individual happiness secured only within a political community, or what he calls *polis*. This body politic, he suggests, should organize its institutions to promote what he calls virtuous behaviour because he felt that humans were easily lured to behavioural extremes of one kind or another but that virtue is the path of moderation between the extremes. This virtue leads to a deep well-being, he called *eudaimonia*, which promotes both the psychological strength of the individual and social harmony.

Eudaimonia is sometimes translated as happiness, and often as 'flourishing,' to convey the sense of deep and persistent well-being. Eudaimonia is the *telos*, the end goal of human beings; it is the *summum bonum*, the highest good. Aristotle emphasized that virtue must be cultivated, above all, through the exercise of reason over emotions.¹⁷⁸

Today's literature indicates that political polarization can affect democratic systems and the quality of political debate and capacity. A recent study examined political polarization and economic growth across 75 countries from 1990 to 2019 and found that political polarization negatively impacts economic growth. It also found that strong state capacity, defined as the

government's ability to effectively implement policies, can mitigate the negative effects of polarization on growth.¹⁷⁹

Another study that examined the relationship between political and social trust, government quality, and economic development across 208 regions in the EU finds that political trust serves as a 'fundamental driver of regional economic development in the EU'. It also finds that political trust is, in turn, influenced by both social trust and government quality.¹⁸⁰

Finally, a study of 71 democracies from 1995 to 2019 finds evidence that both left-wing and right-wing governments can deliver convergent outcomes on growth, inflation, inequality and economic freedom in 'consolidated democracies'. These democracies are less active in providing polarized policies and have well-established political systems that are deeply rooted in democratic principles. This concludes that in 'consolidated democracies' a change in government from one political ideology to another with a different ideology does not significantly alter economic policy outcomes.¹⁸¹

Building trust within and across the neighbourhood, city, society, body politic and with neighbouring countries can help us deal more effectively with a crisis.

REFLECTION

We now reflect briefly on certain themes that are important to the above either as further context or relevant detail.

Global Context

Much of the land surface of the Earth has changed considerably since 1800 and this change has been significantly shaped by the growth in human population from 1 billion in 1804 to 8.3 billion today. This is a staggering increase in such a short period of history.¹⁸² During this time, what is now known as the Great Acceleration took place.

Great Acceleration: This refers to the period of extremely rapid growth in human activity beginning in the mid-20th century. Here world population growth shifted from a steady increase to a sharp, exponential rise driven by advances in a range of areas including medicine, agriculture, sanitation, and technology.

Although most of the population growth since 1950 has been in the non-OECD world, the world's economy is significantly influenced by the OECD.

The diagrams on the next page indicate the rapid acceleration of world population, urban population, and GDP since 1950 along with terrestrial biosphere degradation, carbon dioxide growth, and ocean acidification. Along with the other results in the original article this points to a post-1950 acceleration in the state and functioning of the Earth System driven by human activity.

Since 1950, according to the evidence, the 'most rapid transformation of the human relationship with the natural world in the history of humankind' has taken place within which 'biodiversity loss may be approaching mass extinction rates'.¹⁸³

Global Indicators of Socio-Economic & Earth System Trends (1750-2010).¹⁸⁴

The Safe Surface of the Natural World

A recent message from the cyber security section in TU Dublin refers to its work on strengthening the 'attack surface' of the university's digital systems. Safeguarding the attack surface in cyber security terms means identifying and minimizing all possible points where an unauthorized user can try to enter or extract data from a system.¹⁸⁵

Using this concept as metaphor, we can refer to the safe surface of the natural world and how it has been weakened over time. The eight-fold increase in world population and all that went with it since 1800 has put significant pressure on the natural world and its ecosystems. On the other side of the safe surface of the natural world are the factors that weaken it.

Externalities: Some of these factors have been conceptualised by, for example, economics with the concept of negative externalities. An externality is an external activity to an economic transaction that can affect third parties that are not part of the transaction and whose impact is not reflected in market prices. These effects can be positive or negative, but in environmental terms such as pollution or biodiversity loss, they are typically negative.

Pollution is a negative externality when farming or industry in producing goods for the consumer, pollute the air, water, or soil. Biodiversity is similarly damaged when deforestation, or urbanisation reduce species richness, and weaken ecosystems and climate resilience.¹⁸⁶

Ecological vulnerability refers to the susceptibility of an ecosystem to adverse effects. This susceptibility can be evaluated using indicators from natural, social, and economic systems, often facilitated by remote sensing technology.¹⁸⁷

Strengthening the safe surface of the natural world is what this report is really about. Having discussed the problems of the natural world we find that Ireland with its strong economy, stable political system, EU membership and neighbourhood archipelago, has a significantly damaged natural world and a biodiversity intactness that is extremely poor by global standards.

Intrapreneurial spirit: The work of the Parks, Biodiversity and Landscape Services division of Dublin City Council, in upkeeping, improving and, extending the city's parks, gardens, trees and green spaces helps to enhance the safe surface of the city's natural world. The work also reflects an intrapreneurial spirit. Intrapreneurs are those employees of a private or public sector organisation who use the organisation's resources to develop innovative actions, products, or services.

In addition, for example, the council's research into algal blooms in Dublin Bay, marine invasive species, the monitoring of bird species, radio tracking to research foraging strategies of urban foxes and their role in rodent control, sampling environmental DNA to estimate the city's otter population, and installing artificial habitats to increase biodiversity helps to strengthen the city's contribution to the safe surface of the natural world. The council also carries out citizen science workshops, walks, talks and workshops, and exhibits at the Rose Festival in St Anne's Park and Bloom in the Phoenix Park. It has received a variety of Green Flag awards for its parks over the years and new parks continue to be opened and redeveloped. Links to its most recent delivery plans are provided in the footnote where the Bull Island Nature Reserve is listed under its parks management and development work.¹⁸⁸ It has also introduced a pesticide reduction strategy to make parks and open spaces 'chemical free', changed mowing regimes and increased pollinator friendly planting regimes along with a variety of other activities.¹⁸⁹ Those who benefit from its parks, gardens, trees, footpath flowers, and shrub spaces are very lucky.¹⁹⁰

To support and strengthen all of this good work, they should withdraw the Discovery Centre proposal for the Bull Island Nature Reserve and replace it with a Distributed Learning Network or something similar that will be widely available to all its citizens. (Appendix 2.)

Visitors, Sustainable Tourism & De-urbanisation

Dublin City Council states that the 'entire focus of the Discovery Centre is on education, interpretation and learning with a view to enhanced conservation. It is not a centre for tourism'.¹⁹¹

Fáilte Ireland, the state's tourism board, was involved in the 2013 tender, as mentioned earlier. Its involvement under 'strategic infrastructure project' is indicated by Dublin City Council in a presentation of the centre's construction costs in 2018. The centre's 'self-funding model', and staffing categories (centre manager, exhibition manager, visitor experience head, visitor guides, volunteers) are also mentioned.¹⁹²

The Discovery Centre proposal comes under the Dublin Bay UNESCO Biosphere which is managed by a partnership that includes Fáilte Ireland as part of the 'sustainable development' of the Dublin Bay UNESCO Biosphere.¹⁹³

Fáilte Ireland's involvement, the self-funding model, and the 'sustainable development' approach need further reflection.

Overtourism, Sustainable Tourism & De-urbanisation: Overtourism is the 'excessive negative impact of tourism on the host communities and/or natural environment'. This concept has garnered greater interest since COVID-19. Some have also stated that the 'intellectually

appealing theoretical concept of sustainable tourism has little practical application ... allowing essentially the same behaviour as before'.¹⁹⁴

Overtourism also involves 'the use of tourism destinations' natural ecological goods' and other activities which have 'rendered tourism irresponsible.' This has led to a 'stronger focus on implementing responsible tourism'. Despite this development, 'overtourism still occurs ... providing the strongest practical evidence so far of the illusiveness of a sustainable and responsible tourism paradigm'.¹⁹⁵

Making a distinction made between 'visitors' to the Bull Island Nature Reserve and 'tourists' is a moot point and irrelevant to the visitor pressures that would arise from introducing such a 'gateway' to the reserve.¹⁹⁶

By contrast, the wetland restoration in La Pletera salt marsh on the coast of Catalonia, restored with EU funding, is worth mentioning here. This was a demonstration project of de-urbanisation and ecological restoration of a coastal ecosystem threatened by human pressure mainly due to tourism and climate change.

The restoration work consisted of removing urban infrastructure (breakwater, paved streets, road accesses and filling material dumped into the salt marsh), eliminating all the built infrastructure and lowering the land topography to its original level. In addition, 21 artificial lagoons were developed in parallel bands to the beach, emulating the natural structure of a coastal marsh.¹⁹⁷

This type of approach is important because it reverses the old assumption that conservation success requires on site visitor facilities. Instead, this new thinking asks - which built structures should not exist in ecologically stressed landscapes and climate fragile locations like Dublin Bay?

Biosphere Reserves

Our earlier discussion about the UNESCO Dublin Bay Biosphere Reserve designation adding to the pressures on Bull Island is further supported by a recent review of the literature. This shows that the assumed win-win outcomes in biodiversity protection and socioeconomic development in Biosphere Reserves is not guaranteed and this can be linked to the fact that Biosphere Reserves are not classified within the global conservation frameworks.

This review also indicates that Biosphere Reserves can become 'mini public authorities', taking on a life of their own and develop institutional elements such as steering committees and other structures which can allow them to come adrift of central government's biodiversity objectives.¹⁹⁸

Might it not be better to focus on the global conservation frameworks and legislation rather than the Biosphere Reserve framework which trying to be both conservation and development fails on both counts? Should the biodiversity emergency not stand clear of visitor centres and self-funding concerns and be its own challenge and in the process help deal with the climate challenge?

The Home Space

We look briefly at the garden or external space of a home, and the estate or local neighbourhood of a home.

Gardens: Gardening is one of the most common ways to connect with nature. According to a report by the Royal Horticultural Society, gardens are biodiversity hotspots and climate allies covering 4.6% of Great Britain's land area – over three times the size of UK National Nature Reserves – and supporting over 50 million trees and thousands of species. In addition, they provide habitat for over 40% of bird and mammals species, and more than half of butterfly, amphibian and reptile species.

UK gardens store an estimated 158 million tonnes of carbon, equivalent size for size to a 30-year-old native woodland, and deliver over 45 ecosystem services. Gardens are no longer just safe areas for nature, they are 'ecological powerhouses' and critical components of the biodiversity network.

To realise the full potential of gardens, 'we must embed gardening in national health, education, housing and climate policy' and 'invest in research, infrastructure and equitable access'. In all of this the report proposes that gardens must be recognised as 'critical national assets – ecologically, socially and economically'. In the end, gardens are not just private spaces – they are also 'shared national assets' and a 'massive but overlooked ecological asset, that buffer the effects of climate change and bring joy to millions'. Around 60% of the UK population did gardening at least once a month in 2024.¹⁹⁹

Although the total network of domestic gardens could make a significant contribution to biodiversity enhancement and climate resilience, they are managed by different types of gardeners, many of whom prioritise aesthetics and maintenance convenience over biodiversity enhancement and climate resilience. Understanding how gardeners operate and make decisions is important for unlocking the biodiversity and climate potential of the garden network.

A recent study looks at what drives gardeners' decision making and focuses on why people manage their gardens in particular ways, and how their decisions affect climate change adaptation and urban environmental resilience.

It considers the impact of knowledge, social-economic context (income, education, household size), and spatial context (garden size, house type, level of residency, urbanisation) and how environmental attitudes affect gardening decision making.

The finding that knowledge alone has a limited impact on gardeners' decision making led the authors to advise that 'policy efforts focused solely on providing information may not be sufficient to drive significant changes'. The report suggests that although good information is necessary it is also important to actively engage people through briefings, presentations, courses, interactive awareness programs, and participatory initiatives, to strengthen the impact of the new knowledge. This finding rhymes with the suggestion of a Distributed Learning Network. (Appendix 3).

Incentives that reduce socio-economic barriers such as subsidies for tree planting, and physical assistance for pavement removal or tree management. Compulsory measures restricting garden composition choices through laws, regulations and mandates, or financial tools such as taxes

are also listed. For example, a tax per square meter on sealed soil to limit further soil sealing which could be tailored for areas with high soil sealing or high flooding risk.

The study concludes by proposing a biodiversity enhancement and climate resilience land use policy for gardens that incorporates both adjustment measures such as regulations and taxes with voluntary strategies such as incentives and engagement initiatives.²⁰⁰

Below is a simple image of a biodiverse and climate resilient garden. The greenery and open vegetation provides a 'sponge' habitat for heavy rain and storms and vegetation and native plants for biodiversity and carbon sequestration. The boundary hedging replaces the boundary fences and walls found in many dwellings and estates. As well as providing greater biodiversity they offer natural corridors for hedgehogs, foxes, frogs and other creatures to move more safely from one place to another. For those with wooden fencing ground level openings can provide a corridor effect.

Biodiverse Garden²⁰¹

THE FUTURE

There is a certain helplessness among people about our ability to deal with the crisis. This is unnecessary. The scientific evidence and best practice examples across the world tell us how best to deal with the challenge.

However, we have a tendency to think that solutions lie somewhere else. When we consider the great Serengeti, the vast Arctic tundra, the Eurasian Steppe, the Amazon rainforest, and the Great Barrier Reef, we feel it is all happening elsewhere.

Many of us living in cities, towns, and urban complexes often feel that the great outdoors and the solutions to our biodiversity and climate crises lie somewhere else.

We can watch the wonders of the natural world through modern communications. Dolphins, tigers, flying geese, vast forests and grasslands can enter our living room, office, or train journey in full digital colour at any time of the day or night.

There is a real desire among people to have the great outdoors made whole and a great hope that others out there can do it for us. Many would like to visit these natural wonders, sometimes

over great distances, but can miss the fact that the greatness of the natural world is right around us. We rarely connect our local gardens, hedgerows, trees, green spaces, farms, and bird life to the vast expanses of elsewhere.

Everything cannot be solved elsewhere. Every place can have its own green space. Everyone can help in their own way and enjoy doing it.

This report makes a number of proposals to help resolve the biodiversity and related climate resilience crisis. None of these are perfect.

The most important ingredient in dealing with the crisis is a common understanding of what is going on and a focused and shared effort in helping to resolve it.

There is no shopping list of perfect solutions. Finding the best path forward is a bit like crossing the river by feeling the stones.

When the Irish Census time capsules are read by people in 100 years' time we will be long gone but what we do today will affect them greatly, how they live, breathe and prosper.²⁰²

APPENDIX 1 – MAP OF BULL ISLAND

Bull Island contains two golf clubs and a number of natural features.

Dollymount Strand runs along the SE side of the island. Here you can see sanderlings and a variety of other shore birds feeding on the edge of the water.

The *Sand Dune System* has developed over the years and is stabilized by marram grass. Here we also find areas of scrub and marsh (including the Bull Wall Reed Marsh and the Alder Marsh). Birds like skylarks, meadow pipits, reed buntings and stonechats nest here. Shelducks will also nest in a suitable hole in the sand dunes.

The *Salt Marsh* runs along the NW coastline of the island on both sides of the causeway and beside the mudflats. The salt marsh is a coastal wetland where the land meets the sea, and is regularly flooded by tides. It has salt-tolerant plants and is an important habitat for marine and bird life. The Brent Geese often feed here.

The *Mud Flats* lie between the island and the mainland. You can see plenty of waders feeding here between autumn and spring.

The *North & South lagoons* on the landward side of the island are separated by the causeway and consist of both salt marsh and mudflat zones.

APPENDIX 2 – BACKGROUND NOTE

The Discovery Centre Issue

The Discovery Centre proposal has been on-going since at least summer 2018. A discussion with Councillor Horgan-Jones in early 2019 led to a meeting with senior staff in the Parks, Biodiversity and Landscape Services, DCC in March 2019 for which the first draft of *Bull Island's Discovery Centre Proposal: A Review* was written.

Following this, Dublin City Councillors were sent a copy of the updated review in June 2020 and asked if they would request the city manager to consider a more suitable location for the centre. Councillor Tom Brabazon, confirmed he did.²⁰³ Few others replied.

The main conservation groups including An Taisce, Birdwatch Ireland, Dublin Naturalist Field Club and Irish Wildlife Trust (IWT) were also sent a copy of the review and asked to consider taking a position on the issue but none did. One conservation group explained informally that they decided against taking a stand because of concerns about how it might impact on their funding. This funding dilemma has been discussed in the literature.²⁰⁴

An Taisce featured Kerins, A. (2022). [Bull Island's Discovery Centre Proposal: A Review](#) on its website following an [outing](#) to Bull Island on 23 March 2022.

The Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity featured Kerins, A. (2022). [Nature at the edge – Finding a way back](#), 6 June on its repository in 2023. This deals with the biodiversity emergency broadly and treats Bull Island as a case study.

An expanded and updated version of both of these, *Nature at the Edge: Finding a Way Forward*, was submitted to the Taoiseach, the Tánaiste and key cabinet members along with party leaders in Dáil and Seanad Éireann, chairpersons of two Joint Oireachtas Committees, TDs in Dublin North Bay along with the CEOs in the National Parks and Wildlife Services, Environmental Protection Agency, Dublin City Council, Fáilte Eireann and Institute of Public Administration, in September and October 2025.

The 1980's

The Bull Island issue in the early 1980's was somewhat similar. At the time, Dublin Corporation had already built the concrete fence posts to close off parts of the Alder Marsh and incorporate it into St Anne's Golf Club when the main conservation groups were invited to a meeting in the then College of Catering where they were encouraged to take a stand on the issue. Following this meeting and the work that followed, the issue was resolved over a period of time.

Although conservation groups must measure their resources against the battles they fight it is surprising that they have again missed this latest issue on Bull Island, a reserve under huge pressure in the middle of the capital.

It is also of concern how this present Bull Island issue has arisen in the middle of a full-blown biodiversity emergency, over 40 years on from the last one.

A small number of other conservationists have worked on the Discovery Centre issue, in particular Sean Byrne who has also contributed to the debate.²⁰⁵

APPENDIX 3 – DISTRIBUTED LEARNING NETWORK

A Distributed Learning Network (DLN) located within key Dublin parks and other suitable venues to deliver a coordinated public engagement strategy for biodiversity and climate knowledge and understanding. The network would encourage awareness, knowledge-sharing, learning, and where relevant practical experience.

Objective: To strengthen the city as a living ecosystem and reduce the risk of biodiversity loss and climate harm.

Venues

The venues function as learning environments, demonstrating best practice and encouraging wider application across the city and beyond.

Components: Each venue would include three elements:

a) Public-Facing Space

An introductory space providing information and orientation. This would also host briefings and presentations on a scheduled basis.

b) Learning Landscape

An outdoor setting where visitors can experience real-world examples of biodiversity enhancement and/or climate resilience/climate defence features for example:

- *Biodiversity*: woodland edges, deadwood habitats, mature trees, layered vegetation, undisturbed compost-rich soils, leaf litter zones, wildflower meadow, and native hedgerow; natural water, stream or river systems (ponds, gravel beds, meanders, floodplains); green roofs, living walls, and native planting schemes; natural grasslands, seagrass meadows, hill/mountain ecosystems.

*NB: Some biodiversity features can be visited inside the park or venue while others – such as river systems or hill mountain ecosystems are located elsewhere.

- *Climate resilience – Nature Based Solutions (NbS)*: wetlands, salt marshes, bogs, coastal dune systems, oyster reefs, barrier island, forests, healthy soil, urban green space, natural grassland, floodplains and strengthening and restoration of these features – for example rewetting of bogs and paludiculture in the footnote.²⁰⁶ See also Appendix 5.

*NB: Some NbS features can be visited inside the park or venue while many of the others – such as barrier island, wetlands, floodplains, bogs are located elsewhere.

- *Climate defences – Structural/Built Solutions*: walls, ramparts, embankments, barricades, water management systems (storm surge gates, 'smart sewer systems', hardened energy grids, and buried utility lines).

*NB: Most defence features will be located or developed elsewhere over time.

- *Hybrid defences* that blend engineering with ecology; for example—a concrete sea wall integrated into a reconstructed sand dune, bioswales or 'living' sea walls designed to host marine life.²⁰⁷

*NB: Most hybrid features will be located or developed elsewhere over time.

c) Operational Learning Space

A hands-on learning environment supporting information, workshops, demonstrations, and practical guidance.

Operation & Spatial Structure

Visitors arrive at entrance point and are directed to interpretive routes throughout the park. General access is walk-in, while briefings, workshops, and core learning activities would be scheduled or booked.

A. Entrance / Orientation

Provides public visibility, orientation, and interpretation.

Includes a small exhibition and presentation space for talks, visits, and events.

B. Learning Landscape

A network of trails, low-impact signage, and habitat examples distributed across the park.

Supported by a digital layer (e.g. QR codes) for interpretation.

C. Learning and Demonstration Zone

Located within the operational landscape of the venue. Supports hands-on education, workshops, and pilot projects in biodiversity and climate resilience.

Access managed through booking.

Resources:

Centres are supported by administrative staff and skilled professionals, including practitioners and scientists in biodiversity and climate resilience.

Fees: Specialist courses and training programmes operate on a community fee basis.

Funding sources: city, national, EU.

Governance & Standards

DLNs would be certified at national level, aligned with international best practice.

Certification would be renewed every five years, with provision for annual review.

Development Stages

Feasibility study, followed by a pilot project and evaluation phase.

Subject to success, the network would be rolled out gradually and strategically.

Individual sites may operate under fixed-term agreements (e.g. six-year contracts).

Conclusion

This strategy maximises the use of existing infrastructure, avoids the need for major new builds and supports biodiversity and climate literacy across the city.

By embedding learning within the landscape, it transforms parks and similar venues into environmental learning systems, creating a scalable model for Dublin and beyond.

APPENDIX 4 – LOCAL NATURE AREAS

Every community deserves its own nature area where people can relax and enjoy their part of the great outdoors. Ireland has many potential areas that could be cared for and developed for the mutual benefit of people and biodiversity ranging from small green spaces to larger areas.

Local Community Nature Area

There are a number of ways to develop a green space into a local nature area and make it into something special for the local community. Some of these are a matter of enhancing the nature and biodiversity quality of a local green space. We can also develop a nature area in a more structured way as follows.

Developing a Local Nature Area in a structured way

Establish an understanding of the site through a *baseline survey* and identify the level and causes of degradation and the opportunities and benefits of improvement.

Protect and stabilise the site by, for example, controlling or preventing pollution damage, erosion, drainage problems and habitat loss.

Rehabilitate and restore the site. For example, restore wetlands, soil, water quality, biodiversity and the community framework of the space so both nature and people thrive.

Safeguard fragile areas, nesting sites, etc.

Encourage the return of wildlife through, for example, vegetation rehabilitating that encourages the safe return of, for example, the corncrake, cuckoo and other forms of nature.

Engage people in the local community, schools, colleges, businesses, public authorities, etc so as to build interest, excitement, support and involvement among young and old.

Inform people about the site, the variety of nature and the related protocols for the safety of people and nature through signage, web, presentations, school visits, etc.

Monitor and track the biodiversity, soil, water, community use and engagement over time.

Adapt and develop the site to become a community nature reserve with no invasive species or dogs. Restoration is a long-term activity.

Adjacency

The World Health Organisation suggests that people living in urban areas should be able to access a public green space of at least 0.5–1 hectare within 300 metres' linear distance of their home and about 5 minutes' walk. Urban Ireland now holds almost 65% of its population. According to the CSO an urban area is a town with 1,500 or more and smaller towns are part of rural areas.²⁰⁸

The Local Bioregion

Protected areas are key elements of the Great Britain, Ireland archipelago and make an important contribution to the overall protection in the region and beyond.

New local nature areas in Ireland could, as they develop and expand, be encouraged to progress and become protected elements of the bioregion. As part of facilitating the visibility of

protected areas, the *Wildling App* could be extended to Ireland to inform and support people in their local area and when they visit other parts of the archipelago.

Ireland

There are 1,222 protected areas dotted throughout Ireland made up of Special Protection Areas, Special Areas of Conservation, Natural Heritage Areas and Proposed National Heritage Areas. See NPWS map below.²⁰⁹

Source: [NPWS Viewer](#).

Wildling App map samples

See Northern Ireland and Scotland taken from the Wildling app below.

[Wildling App](#) ©

APPENDIX 5 – BIODIVERSITY AND CLIMATE CHANGE

Biodiversity and climate change are linked. Improving biodiversity helps mitigate the impact of climate change by, for example, providing nature-based solutions like restoring fens, wetlands and bogs.

When we produce greenhouse gases around half of the emissions remain in the atmosphere, while the other half is absorbed by the land and ocean where certain ecosystems are natural carbon sinks. Forests, wetlands, marshes and swamps are important here. Although peatlands such as marshes and swamps cover only 3 per cent of the land area of the world they store twice as much carbon as all the forests. Preserving and restoring peatlands means keeping them wet so the carbon does not oxidize and float off into the atmosphere.²¹⁰

Case – Wicken Fen Reserve

Wicken Fen is an important example of a nature reserve linking biodiversity improvement to climate change. The National Trust established it in 1899 by buying 2 acres of Wicken Fen.

The reserve then expanded to around 358 hectares by 1999. At the time, however, it was seen as too small to guarantee the survival of all its species and had also been under pressure from the increasing number of people using the reserve.²¹¹ Consequently, the National Trust launched a 100-year plan to expand its size to 5,300 hectares bringing it to the edge of Cambridge.²¹²

In the last 25 years, the reserve has more than doubled in size making it one of the most important wetlands reserves in Europe.²¹³ It has also provided a location for important scientific enquiry over the years. For example, one of the most significant studies of the cuckoo was based here over the years.²¹⁴ However, it is the ambitious expansion plans for the reserve that sets it apart as an important example of biodiversity improvement and climate resilience.

As Wicken Fen Reserve expands into the future it will improve the carbon sequestration and flood and drought protection of the area through its increasing capacity to maintain a high water table and reduce the impact of flooding downstream. Its dynamic wetland habitat will, therefore, help to buffer the impact of flooding caused by higher rainfall and rising sea levels over time.²¹⁵

This approach to habitat improvement will be important to consider across all water systems in Ireland including the Shannon basin and other major catchment areas throughout the country. So, as we make habitat improvements in our local areas, we should also consider how these developments might also contribute to flood, water and level sea management and climate change.

[Wicken Fen](#)

Addendum

This is a working draft that has evolved from earlier works, as mentioned in Appendix 2.

The references are integrated into the footnotes.

The original source of each image is, where possible, indicated in a hyperlink or footnote.

My thanks to Sean Byrne for reviewing the main text. Any remaining errors are entirely my own. Sean has also contributed over time to the ongoing debate on the Discovery Centre proposal and other biodiversity issues on Bull Island.

The literature research and information gathering element of the work benefited from the use of:

- TU Dublin's IReL (Irish Research eLibrary) access to electronic journals, databases, and e-books.²¹⁶
- Articles, books, and reports provided on an open access basis.
- Large Language Models (in particular, Google Gemini, OpenAI ChatGPT, Anthropic Claude and Google Chrome AI Mode (Discover / Feed Suggestions)).

The approach to the work has been informed over time by a variety of factors including an interest in the wellbeing of others and an enjoyment of the natural world.

Anto Kerins

Notes

¹ See National Aeronautics and Space Administration. (2003). [Viewing Earth's limb](#). NASA Earth Observatory, April 2, and Wilkinson, J. (2022). [Earth's limb with a crescent moon](#), NASA Earth Observatory, August 21.

² See Radowitz, J. (2017). [Stephen Hawking says we must colonise other planets to ensure human survival](#). *The Independent*, May 20.

³ See Musk, E. (2017). [Making Humans a Multi-Planetary Species](#), *New Space*, 5(2), 46-61, p. 46.

⁴ Ireland ranks second in the European Union in terms of GDP per capita. See European Union. (n.d.). [Ireland](#), in European Union – Countries, retrieved January 8, 2026. Ireland ranks fourth in the world in Price, C. (2025). [The Richest Countries in the World](#), 24 October, *World Atlas*, retrieved January 8, 2026. In considering these rankings, we must mention the large impact on Irish GDP of multinationals. Consequently, other metrics like GNI and modified domestic demand are often used to more accurately reflect underlying living standards.

The population figure is based on the CSO April 2025 estimate of 5.46 million and the Budget 2026 demographic impact assessment, which projects a continued annual growth rate of approximately 1.2% driven by high levels of inward migration. See CSO (2025) [Population and Migration Estimates, April 2025](#) and Parliamentary Budget Office. (2025). [Costing Analysis on Estimated Existing Level of Service Costs for 2026](#). Houses of the Oireachtas. October 3. See also European Commission, Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs. (2025, November 17). [Economic forecast for Ireland](#). European Commission. Retrieved January 8, 2026.

Ireland came third in the world with the most unspoilt landscapes in one source. See, [Inghams \(2023\) Instagram Top 20 Countries With the Most Unspoilt Landscapes](#). There is also research over several decades which consistently demonstrates the high premium tourists place upon Ireland's natural environment and landscape'. See Irish Travel Industry Confederation (2014) [Protecting the Irish Environment and Landscape: A Critical Issue for Irish Tourism](#) - Position Paper by CHL Consulting Ltd., p. i.

However, while the Irish landscape looks fresh and green, Ireland has, for example, only the third lowest forest cover in Europe (11.6%), with an EU-27 with an average of 38.8%. Source: Central Statistics Office. (2025). [Environmental indicators Ireland 2024: Land use](#), January 29.

This indicates that much of the 'unspoilt' green that people see is actually managed agricultural land rather than natural wilderness or woodlands and peoples' understandable enthusiasm for the Emerald Isle has little to do with biodiversity and wild nature.

The term Emerald Isle was coined by William Drennan and appeared in his 1795 poem 'When Erin First Rose.' See Ó Cuív, B. (1977). [The Wearing of the Green](#). *Studia Hibernica*, 17/18, 107–119, p. 116-117.

However, the conceptualisation and use of the Emerald Isle with closeness to nature has been criticised. For example, one source states that 'the Celtic Tiger years successfully relied on, and reflected, a dual picture of global business attractiveness and unspoiled nature ... as the ideal setting for pharmaceutical and IT companies.' Here nature is used 'as a focal point in the stereotypical representations of Ireland ... as part of the nation's brand' and the concept of the Emerald Isle 'conveniently contributes to the country's perceived closeness with the natural environment. Only after the fall of the Celtic Tiger did another landscape begin to emerge: that of a dilapidated, polluted environment ... (placing) Ireland onto a global map of environmental crises and largely debunking a myth that is still desperately advertised by the national tourism industry today.' See for example, Conan, C. and Coulouma, F. (2019). Introduction. [Études irlandaises](#), 44(1), 7–15, p. 7.

⁵ A review of the literature found an association between nature exposure and improved cognitive function, brain activity, blood pressure, mental health, physical activity, and sleep. This discusses the 'biophilia hypothesis' which suggests that humans have evolved with nature to have an affinity for it. This hypothesis has two underpinning theories. First, Attention Restoration Theory which suggests that the mental fatigue of modern life is associated with a weakened capacity to direct attention. According to this, time spent in nature enables people to overcome this fatigue and restore their capacity to pay attention. Second, Stress Reduction Theory which describes how spending time in nature may influence feelings or emotions that reduce stress and involuntary arousal because of our innate connection to nature. See Jimenez, M. P., DeVille, N. V., Elliott, E. G., Schiff, J. E., Wilt, G. E., Hart, J. E., and James, P. (2021) [Associations between Nature Exposure and Health: A Review of the Evidence](#), *International Journal of Environmental Research in Public Health*, Apr 30; 18(9), 4790.

Another review found that exposure to urban nature provides substantial mental health benefits which was most pronounced among young adults and consistently positive across all age groups. See Li, Y., Mao, Y., Mandle, L., Rydström, A., Remme, R. P., Lan, X., Wu, T., Song, C., Lu, Y., Nadeau, K. C., Meyer-Lindenberg, A., Daily, G. C., and Guerry, A. D. (2025) [Acute mental health benefits of urban nature](#), *Nature Cities* 2, 720–731.

⁶ See Nguyen, P.-Y., Astell-Burt, T., Rahimi-Ardabili, H., & Feng, X. (2023) [Effect of nature prescriptions on cardiometabolic and mental health, and physical activity: a systematic review](#), *The Lancet Planetary Health*, vol. 7, issue 4. See also CSO (2025) [Recreation in Nature - How We Spent Summer 2024](#), 06 June. This found that wellness and well-being were the main reasons people said they spent time in nature. Here 60% of people spent time in nature for physical health and exercise, 59% to get fresh air, and 55% for mental health and well-being. (figure/table 2.1). Nearly 90% of people reported feeling happier after spending time in nature and 82% said they felt less stressed and/or anxious. (tables 2.2 and 2.5)

⁷ See, for example, [World Wildlife Fund](#). World Wildlife Fund. (n.d.). [Valuing nature](#). WWF UK. Retrieved January 8, 2026. This states that the natural assets in nature are often called the world's 'natural capital' which are very important to the economy – from farming and forestry to leisure and tourism. If you add them all up, the total value of these benefits is at least US\$125 trillion every year.

⁸ See Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. (2019). [Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services](#) (S. Díaz *et al.*, Eds.). IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany, ps. 10-12, 14, 22-23, 52. See also National Academies of Sciences,

Engineering & Medicine. (2022). [Biodiversity at Risk: Today's Choices Matter](#), Washington, DC: The National Academies Press, p. 1, 11.

⁹ See Hoffmann, S., (2022). [Challenges and opportunities of area-based conservation in reaching biodiversity and sustainability goals](#). *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 31, 325–352, p. 325-326.

See also ICUN's helpful classification of protected areas below:

1. *a: Strict Nature Reserve*: Strictly protected for biodiversity and possibly geological/geomorphological features, where visitors' use and impacts are controlled and limited.
b: Wilderness area: Large unmodified or slightly modified areas, retaining their natural character, without permanent or significant habitation, protected and managed to preserve their natural condition.
2. *National Park*: Large natural or near-natural areas protecting large-scale ecological processes with characteristic species and ecosystems, providing scientific, educational, and recreational opportunities.
3. *Natural monument or feature*
4. *Habitat/species management area*
5. *Protected landscape or seascape*
6. *Protected areas with sustainable use of natural resources*

Source: Dudley, N., Ed. (2008) [Guidelines for Applying Protected Area Management Categories](#), IUCN, p i.

¹⁰ See Achiso, Z. (2020). [Biodiversity and Human Livelihoods in Protected Areas: Worldwide Perspective - A Review](#). *SSR Institute of International Journal of Life Sciences*, 6, 2565-2578 , p. 2565-2566.

¹¹ See UNEP-WCMC and IUCN (2024). [Protected Planet Report 2024](#), UNEP-WCMC and IUCN: Cambridge, United Kingdom; Gland, Switzerland, p. 2 and 14.

¹² On the above see Dinerstein, E., Vynne, C., Sala, E., Joshi, A. R., Fernando, S., Lovejoy, T. E., Mayorga, J., Olson, D., Asner, G. P., Baillie, J. E. M., Burgess, N. D. (2019). [A Global Deal For Nature: Guiding principles, milestones, and targets](#). *Science Advances*, 5 (4), 19 April, p. 1, 4, 12.

¹³ See Convention on Biological Diversity. (n.d.). [Target 3: Conserve 30% of land, waters and seas](#), Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and Convention on Biological Diversity. (2022). [Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework](#) (CBD/CP/MOP/DEC/15/4). United Nations.

¹⁴ See International Union for Conservation of Nature. (2023). [IUCN WCPA Technical Note Series No. 8 \(updated October 2023\): Role of protected areas in climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation. World](#), Commission on Protected Areas, p.4.

¹⁵ An important study on irrecoverable carbon and its mapping is Noon, M. L., Goldstein, A., Ledezma, J. C., Roehrdanz, P. R., Cook-Patton, S. C., Spawn-Lee, S. A., Wright, T. M., Gonzalez-Roglich, M., Hole, D. G., Rockström, J., & Turner, W. R. (2022). [Mapping the irrecoverable carbon in Earth's ecosystems](#). *Nature Sustainability*, 5(1), 37–46.

¹⁶ See UNEP. (2024). [World must act faster to protect 30% of the planet by 2030](#), 28 October.

¹⁷ See WWF. (2000). [Protected Areas or Paper Parks?](#), 1 June and WildAid Marine (2021) [Looks Good on Paper: Addressing the Problem of Paper Parks](#), Mary Pantenburg, 29 March and Stephenson, F., Horta e Costa, B., Addamo, A.M. *et al.* (2025). [Quality of marine protected areas is critical to achieving global biodiversity targets](#). *npj Ocean Sustain* 4, 63. See also Li, G., Fang, C., Watson, J.E.M., Sun, S., Qi, W., Wang, Z., Liu, J. (2024). [Mixed effectiveness of global protected areas in resisting habitat loss](#). *Nature Communications*, 15, 8389.

¹⁸ See Cintio, A. D., Niccolini, F., Scipioni, S. & Bulleri, F. (2023). [Avoiding 'Paper Parks': A Global Literature Review on Socioeconomic Factors Underpinning the Effectiveness of Marine Protected Areas](#). *Sustainability*, 15 (5), 1-19.

¹⁹ See Laurance, W. F., Useche, D. C., Rendeiro, J., Kalka, M., Bradshaw, C. J. A., Sloan, S. P., Laurance, S. G., Campbell, M., Danielsen, F., *et al.* [Averting biodiversity collapse in tropical forest protected areas](#), *Nature* 489, 290–294.

²⁰ See European Environment Agency. (2025a). [Europe's Environment 2025 – Main Report, Europe's environment and climate: knowledge for resilience, prosperity and sustainability](#), 28 September.

²¹ See European Environment Agency. (2025b). [Monitoring report on the progress towards the 8th EAP objectives 2025](#). 10 December.

²² See European Environment Agency. (n.d.). [Ireland](#). Biodiversity Information System for Europe. Retrieved January 12, 2026.

²³ See Government of Ireland (2024) [Ireland's 4th National Biodiversity Action Plan 2023–2030](#), Department of Housing, Housing and Heritage, January p. 6 and 16. See also Wall, B. Cahalane, A. and Derham, J. Eds., (2020) [Ireland's Environment – An Integrated Assessment](#), Environmental Protection Agency, November, p. 12 and 411.

²⁴ The Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII) was developed by the Natural History Museum in London as a summary measure of the state of biodiversity. It seeks to summarise the change in ecological conditions as a result of human influence. It is defined as ‘an estimated percentage of the original number of species that remain and their abundance in any given area, despite human impacts’. See Cathal, N., Fitzgerald, C., (2023). [Is Ireland thriving? Answers from international assessments](#), National Economic and Social Council, Secretariat Paper No. 32, p. 6 and 29. See also Harding, J. (2025). [Ireland's habitats loss continues](#). *Butterfly Conservation Ireland*, June 15 and Natural History Museum. (n.d.). [Biodiversity indicators](#).

²⁵ See European Environment Agency. (2025c). [Europe's Environment 2025, Country profile: Ireland](#), 28 September and Government of Ireland. (2024). [Ireland's 4th National Biodiversity Action Plan 2023–2030](#), Department of Housing, Housing and Heritage, January p. 6 and 16. See also Wall, B. *et al.*, Eds., (2020). p. 12, 153 and 411. See also National Parks & Wildlife Service. (2025). [The status of EU protected habitats and species in Ireland: Volume 1 – Summary overview](#), (Article 17 Report, 2025). Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, 11 December, p. 79, 96.

²⁶ See Möller, I. & O’Leary, K. (2025). [Balancing conservation and human access to nature: the impact of a constructed causeway on water levels and sedimentation, North Bull Island, Ireland](#). *Cambridge Prisms: Coastal Futures*, 3, e9, 1–12 and National Parks and Wildlife Service. (2014). [North Bull Island SPA](#), Site Synopsis, 25 March.

²⁷ See National Parks and Wildlife Service. (2023). [Information Sheet on Ramsar Wetlands \(RIS\) for North Bull Island, Site no. 406](#). Ramsar Sites Information Service, 7 March.

²⁸ National Parks & Wildlife Service. (n.d.). [North Bull Island Nature Reserves](#). Department of Housing, Local Government & Heritage. Retrieved January 12, 2026.

²⁹ See McCorry, M. and Ryle, T. (2009). [A Management plan for North Bull Island](#), Dublin City Council.

³⁰ North Bull Island supports nine habitats and a range of species protected under the EU Habitats Directive. It is recognised by Bird Life International as a key part of the East Atlantic Flyway for migrant birds travelling from the Canadian Arctic to the Mediterranean region and Africa. It also supports a range of overwintering wildfowl and wading birds protected under the EU Birds Directive.

North Bull Island is a National Nature Reserve (NNR) under the Wildlife Act. All wildlife and habitats within the Bull Island NNR both on the island and inter-tidal areas are fully protected by Irish and European legislation. The abbreviated terms ‘Bull Island’ and ‘Nature Reserve’ are used for convenience. When we refer to them in the singular we do so for convenience as there are more correctly two reserves. These comprise 1,436 hectares, of which 1,318 are State-owned and 118 are privately owned. ([Source](#)).

The details of the North Bull Island Special Protection Area (SPA) can be seen [here](#). The North Dublin Bay Special Area of Conservation (SAC) site covers the inner part of north Dublin Bay, the seaward boundary from the Bull Wall lighthouse to the Martello Tower at Howth Head. The North Bull Island is the focal point of this site. (See [here](#) and [here](#)).

See Dublin City Council’s useful [list of designations](#) and [North Bull Island Dublin Bay Wildlife](#) and [Birds of Bull Island](#) both of which are important sources of information on the island.

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- ³¹ The core conservation zone of the Dublin Bay Biosphere covers 50km², the buffer zone, surrounding or adjoining the core zones, covers 82km² of green spaces such as parks, greenbelts and golf courses and the transition zone with 173km² forms the outer part of the biosphere and includes residential areas, harbours, ports and industrial and commercial areas. See Department of Jobs, Enterprise and Innovation. (2015). [UNESCO biosphere status for Dublin Bay will enhance development of “green city by the sea”](#) 24 June, UNESCO. (n.d.). [World Network of Biosphere Reserves: About biosphere reserves](#), UNESCO. (n.d.). [Dublin Bay](#), EPA Catchments Unit. (2016). [Dublin Bay – A UNESCO Biosphere](#). Catchments.ie. July 12.
- ³² See Reid, N. (2011). [European hare \(*Lepus europaeus*\) invasion ecology: Implication for the conservation of the endemic Irish hare \(*Lepus timidus hibernicus*\)](#). *Biological Invasions*, 13(3), 559-569. See also McCorry, M. and Ryle, T. (2009) p. 44, 61-62 and Favel, N. (2016). [North Bull Island Hare Survey 2016](#), UCD School of Biology and Environment Science. Commissioned by Dublin City Council, p. 24.
- ³³ See National Parks and Wildlife Service. (2013). [Site synopsis: North Dublin Bay SAC \(Site code: 000206\)](#). Department of Arts, Heritage and the Gaeltacht, p. 3 and McCorry, M. and Ryle, T. (2009), p. 44, 61-62.
- ³⁴ See Paschoal, A. M. O., Massara R. L., Bailey L. L., Doherty, Jr., P. F., Santos, P. M., Paglia, A. P. (2018). [Anthropogenic Disturbances Drive Domestic Dog Use of Atlantic Forest Protected Areas](#), *Tropical Conservation Science*, 11.
- ³⁵ See Banks, P. B. & Bryant, J. V. (2007). [Four-legged friend or foe? Dog walking displaces native birds from natural areas](#). *Biology Letters*, 3(6), 611–613, p. 611-612.
- ³⁶ See Favel, N. (2016). [North Bull Island Hare Survey 2016](#), UCD School of Biology and Environment Science. Commissioned by Dublin City Council.
- ³⁷ See Paschoal, *et al.*, (2018).
- ³⁸ See Doolan, G. & Hynes, S. (2026). [Estimating the change in recreational value when limits are placed on access to a protected coastal area](#), *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 69:5, 1479-1502, p. 1483.
- ³⁹ See Dublin City Council. (2023). [Visitor Access Management Plan - Signage](#) [PDF].
- ⁴⁰ See Dublin City Council. (2023a). [Visitor Access Management Plan](#), 30 April and Dublin City Council. (2025). [Chief Executive’s Management Report](#), January.
- ⁴¹ See McMahon, B. J., Doyle, S., Mougeot, F., & Arroyo, B. (2024) [The decline of ground nesting birds in Europe: Do we need to manage predation in addition to habitat?](#) *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 55, e03213, p. 1, 2, 6, 8 and McMahon, B. J., Doyle, S., Gray, A., Kelly, S. B. A., & Redpath, S. M. (2020). [European bird declines: Do we need to rethink approaches to the management of abundant generalist predators?](#) *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 10, 1885–1895, p. 1885, 1887, 1888.
- ⁴² See Thomas, R.L., Papworth, S.K. & Fellowes, M. D. (2024). [Unleashed: walking dogs off the lead greatly increases habitat disturbance in UK lowland heathlands](#), *Urban Ecosystems* 27, 2037–2046, p. 2037, 2042.
- ⁴³ See Lauder, A. & Riley M. (2017). [Managing the Impact of Dogs and Dog Walkers on Biodiversity, North Bull Island Nature Reserve, Dublin](#), 12 May, Draft Report. Prepared for Dublin City Council, p. 26.
- ⁴⁴ See Bournemouth, Christchurch and Poole Council (BCP Council). (n.d.). [Dogs on lead season in nature reserves](#) and UK Government. (n.d.). [Controlling your dog in public: Public Spaces Protection Orders](#). GOV.UK.
- ⁴⁵ See the section: 'The details on the obligation to wear a lead in protected areas and conservation areas' where it states that: 'Anyone who intentionally or negligently fails to keep dogs on a leash in violation of these regulations is committing an administrative offense that can be punished with a fine.' See Stadt Salzgitter. (n.d.). [Leinenpflicht](#).
- ⁴⁶ On research see for example, Wilson, L. J., Rendell-Read, S., Lock, L., Drewitt, A. L., & Bolton, M. (2020). [Effectiveness of a five-year project of intensive, regional-scale, coordinated management for little terns *Sternula albifrons* across the major UK colonies](#), *Journal for Nature Conservation*. Volume 53.

See also Simmons, R. (2001) [Successful Conservation measures and new breeding records for Damara Terns *Sterna balaenarum* in Namibia](#). *Marine Ornithology*, 29: 81–84.

On protection zone and fencing projects see for example, Royal Society for the Protection of Birds. (n.d.). [Plovers in peril: Protecting Norfolk's ringed plovers](#) for Ringed Plover fencing and protection, Wildlife Wise. (n.d.). [Kessingland beach-nesting birds](#) for ground nesting birds including Ringed Plover, Little Tern and Oystercatcher and Kavanagh, T. (2022). [Portrane Little Tern/Ringed Plover conservation project](#), Fingal County Council, 2 July. See also BirdWatch Ireland. (n.d.). [Kilcoole Little Tern Project](#) and Heritage Council. (2016). [The Baltray Little Terns conservation scheme](#), August 17 both of which also help to support the safe nesting of Ringed Plover and other birds.

⁴⁷ The hydrology of the dune slacks, and the impact of water extraction/wastewater treatment by St Anne's Golf club has been studied. In addition, one of the golf clubs introduced a reed bed adjacent to the Alder Marsh without any advanced warning and has had overspill of material at its boundary and into the wildlife zones. See Dublin City Council (2020) [North Bull Island Nature Reserve Action Plan 2020-2025 for the Implementation of Management Objectives](#), May, p. 7-8 on the hydrology of the island. See also Dublin City Council, 2020 and McCorry and Ryle, (2009).

⁴⁸ See Dublin City Council. (2026). [Dublin Bay UNESCO Biosphere Discovery Centre](#). Dublin City Council. Retrieved January 13, 2026 and Dublin City Council. (2021b). [Dublin Bay Discovery Centre](#), Update report, Area Committee, May.

⁴⁹ See Dublin City Council. (2021b). p. 1.

⁵⁰ See European Commission. (2020). [Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030: Bringing nature back into our lives](#), [COM(2020) 380 final], p. 2.

⁵¹ See Dublin City Council. (2021a). [Dublin Bay Discovery Centre: Pre-Planning 2021](#), 26 May, presentation, p. 22 and Dublin City Council. (2021b). p. 3.

⁵² See Doolan, G. & Hynes, S. (2026). p. 1494.

⁵³ See Haddad, N. M., Brudvig, L. A., Clobert, J., Davies, K. F., Gonzalez A., Holt, R. D., Lovejoy, T. E., Sexton, J. O., Austin, M.P., Collins, C. D., Cook, W. M., Damschen, E. I., Ewers, R. M., Foster, B. L., Jenkins, C. N., King, A. J., Laurance, W. F., Levey, D. J., Margules, C. R., Townshend, J. R. (2015) [Habitat fragmentation and its lasting impact on Earth's ecosystems](#). *Science Advances*. 20 March;1(2), p. 1- 9. See also Chen Y., Wu, F., Zhang D. & Qiang, Ji. (2025). [International tourism and global biodiversity risks](#), *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 113.

⁵⁴ See Harris, M., Cave, C., Foley, K., Bolger, T., and Hochstrasser, T. (2019) [Urbanisation of Protected Areas within the European Union—An Analysis of UNESCO Biospheres and the Need for New Strategies](#). *Sustainability*, 11(21), 5899, p. 1, 20; Sandström, C., Sahlström, E., & Laudon, H. (2025). [Unlocking the potential of biosphere reserves: A review of structural, institutional, and ideational challenges to transformational learning](#). *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 75, p. 3-4; Amore, A., Adie, B. A., Carnicelli-Filho, S., Lunden, A., & Hall, C. M. (2025). [Planning for sustainable development and tourism in biosphere reserves: A metagovernance appraisal](#). *Tourism Geographies* and Ryan, J., Silvano, S. and Seitz, V. (2013) [The promotion of UNESCO biosphere reserves as tourist destinations: a preliminary examination of trends and implications](#), *Int. J. Business and Globalisation*, Vol. 10, No. 3, pp. 309–324.

⁵⁵ See Article 6 of Council of the European Union. (1992). [Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora](#) (Official Journal L 206, pp. 7–50).

⁵⁶ See European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2024). [Regulation \(EU\) 2024/1991 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2024 on nature restoration and amending Regulation \(EU\) 2022/869](#) (OJ L 199, 29.7.2024).

⁵⁷ See Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage. (2026). [Independent Advisory Committee on Nature Restoration report](#). Government of Ireland, 28 April, p. 5, 12, 27.

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- ⁵⁸ See Dublin City Council. (2013, September 16). [Tender for feasibility study for new interpretive centre and visitor experience at Bull Island](#) (Public Tender No. 70142). eTenders and [Henchion Reuter Architects - Masterplan for Bull Island Visitor Centre](#).
- ⁵⁹ See Fehily Timoney. (2024). [Local Authority Climate Action Plan: Strategic Environmental Assessment Statement](#), Commissioned by Dublin City Council, p. 18-19.
- ⁶⁰ See Howley Hayes Cooney Architects. (2021) [Dublin Bay Discovery Centre](#), Location: Bull Island. Client, Dublin City Council and Dublin City Council. (2021a). p. 13.
- ⁶¹ See [Planning and Development Act 2000](#), No. 30 of 2000 (Ireland), p. 199.
- ⁶² See MCA Architects. (n.d.). [St. Anne's Golf, Enveloped into the Coastal Landscape with a Natural Form](#), Client, St Anne's Golf Club and St Anne's Golf Club, (n.d.). [Club History: Club Centenary](#), Saint Anne's Golf Club North Bull Island.
- ⁶³ See Dublin City Council. (2021a). and Dublin City Council. (2023b). [Capital Programme 2024 – 2026](#), December.
- ⁶⁴ See, for example, Callister, R. (2025). [Retrofit and upgrade vs demolition and rebuild: What's the best option for a developer?](#) May and Urbanist Architecture and Draw Architecture. (2025). [Retrofit vs Demolition](#), DRAW Architecture.
- ⁶⁵ See Zhang, Y., Sattar, S., Cook, D. T., Johnson, K. J. & Fung J. F. (2024). [Systematic Review of Embodied Carbon Assessment and Reduction in Building Life Cycles An Integrated Approach to Resilience and Sustainability](#), *National Institute of Standards and Technology*, U.S. Department of Commerce.
- ⁶⁶ See Dublin City Council. (2022b). [Dublin City Development Plan 2022-2028](#), December, p. 5777.
- ⁶⁷ See Dublin City Council. (2024). [Climate Neutral Dublin 2030, Local Authority Climate, Action Plan 2024-2029](#), March, p. 98 and Government of Ireland. (2026). [The whole-of-government circular economy strategy 2026-2028](#). Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, 24 February, p. 8-9, 32-33.
- ⁶⁸ See European Commission. (2020). p. 6.
- ⁶⁹ See An Comisiún Pleanála. (2025). [Commission order: ABP-319719-24](#). Decision of An Coimisiún Pleanála, p. 4.
- ⁷⁰ See Dublin City Council. (2023b). p. 90.
- ⁷¹ See Department of Public Expenditure, Infrastructure, Public Service Reform and Digitalisation. (2023). [The public spending code](#). Government of Ireland.
- ⁷² See Persson, E. and Tinghög, G. (2020). [Opportunity cost neglect in public policy](#). *Journal of Economic Behaviour & Organization*, 170, 301–312, p. 301, 309, 311
- ⁷³ See Lucas Jr., G. M. (2015, December 17). [Out of sight, out of mind: How opportunity cost neglect undermines democracy](#). *NYU Journal of Law & Liberty*, 9(1), p. 254-255 and 342-343.
- ⁷⁴ See Lindermüller, D., Sohn, M., and Hirsch, B., (2022) [Negative media reporting and its effects on performance information use in public spending](#), *Public Management Review*, 24:7, 1024-1047, p. 1024-1025.
- ⁷⁵ See Dublin City Council. (2021b).
- ⁷⁶ See Environmental Protection Agency. (2025). [National Climate Change Risk Assessment: Main Report](#). Environmental Protection Agency, June, p. 27, 79.
- ⁷⁷ See Environmental Protection Agency. (2025).
- ⁷⁸ See Oireachtas Éireann. (2025a). Question 105 to Minister for Public Expenditure, National Development Plan Delivery & Reform: [The status of coastal flood defences in Dublin Bay](#), April 2. [Written question] and Oireachtas Éireann. (2025b). Question 678 to the Minister for Public Expenditure, National Development Plan Delivery & Reform, [The status of the National Catchment-based Flood Risk Assessment and Management Programme for the Dublin City Council administrative area](#), April 29 [Written question].

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- ⁷⁹ See Murphy, C., Heaphy, L. Quinn, T. O'Brien, E. & Nolan, P. (2023). [Ireland's Climate Change Assessment 2023. Volume 3: Being Prepared for Ireland's Future Climate](#). Environmental Protection Agency, p. 141, 157.
- ⁸⁰ See Central Bank of Ireland. (2024). [Flood Protection Gap Report](#). Central Bank of Ireland, October.
- ⁸¹ See Möller, I. & O'Leary, K. (2025). p. 3 and *passim*. See also Mathew, S., Pellicer, X. M., Caloca, S., Monteys, X., Zarroca, M., & Jiménez-Martín, D. (2019). [Bull Island: Characterisation and development of a modern barrier island triggered by human activity in Dublin Bay, Ireland](#). *Irish Geography*, 52(1), 1–26.
- ⁸² See National Parks & Wildlife Service. (2025). [The status of EU protected habitats and species in Ireland: Volume 1 – Summary overview](#), (Article 17 Report, 2025). Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, 11 December, p. 96 and, for example, Dunne, G., Srinice, E. & Griffin, K. (2020). [The Wild Atlantic Way – A Tourism Journey](#), *Irish Geography*, 53, no. 2, November, 127-144.
- ⁸³ See Möller, I. & O'Leary, K. (2025).
- ⁸⁴ See for example, Lah, O. (2025). [Breaking the silos: integrated approaches to foster sustainable development and climate action](#). *Sustain Earth Reviews* 8, 1, p. 1, 13 and *passim*.
- ⁸⁵ See also Harris, M., Clabby, G., Eakin, M., Farrell, M., Moore, L., Ni'Cholmain, N. & Casey, S. (2014). [North Bull Island UNESCO Biosphere Periodic Review Report](#), September; Whelan, Z. (2018, 14 March). [Council Briefs: The George Bernard Shaw House, Bull Island, and More](#), *Dublin Inquirer*; and Dublin City Council. (2019). [Monthly City Council Meeting](#), 4 March. See also Byrne, S. (2021, 15 November) [Bull island 'Discovery Centre' will hasten precipitous decline of its wildlife. The Centre aims to attract 55,000-60,000 visitors annually](#), *The Village Magazine*; Corrigan, D. (2020, 20 May). [Dublin City Council Propose a New Action Plan for North Bull Island](#), *Dublin Inquirer*, Neylon, L. (2021, 23 June). [A proposed visitor centre and car park won't help preserve Bull Island, local conservationists say](#). *Dublin Inquirer* and Trantum, S. (2024, 20 May). [Department doubtful about council's plan for a new interpretive centre on Bull Island](#), *Dublin Inquirer*.
- ⁸⁶ See R. Shakespeare, Dublin City Council, personal communication, 24 October, 2025; See also Kapila, L. (2026, April 15). [Councillors dig into plan for €3.88 billion in spending on projects in the city](#). *Dublin Inquirer*, Dublin City Council. (2026, April 13). See also Glackin, E. (2026, April 16). [Council managers push forward with plan for a smaller Bull Island Discovery Centre](#). *Dublin Inquirer* and Dublin City Council. (2026). [Report No. 78/2026 of the Chief Executive \(R. Shakespeare\): Capital programme 2026–2028](#), p 70.
- ⁸⁷ See Stake, R. E., (2003). [Case studies](#) in Denzin, N. K. & Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.), *Strategies of Qualitative Inquiry*, (2nd ed., pp. 134–164). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE, p. 137.
- ⁸⁸ See Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage. (2024). [Sustainable residential development and compact settlements: Guidelines for planning authorities](#). Government of Ireland, p. 46.
- ⁸⁹ See Nilon, C. H., Aronson, M. F. J., Cilliers S. S., Dobbs C., Frazee, L. J., Goddard, M. A., O'Neill, K. M., Roberts, D., Stander, E. K., Werner, P., Winter, M., Yocom, K. P., (2017) [Planning for the Future of Urban Biodiversity: A Global Review of City-Scale Initiatives](#), *BioScience*, vol. 67, issue 4, April, p. 332–342.
- ⁹⁰ See Hansen, R., Enderich, L., & Davis, M. (2024). [Urban Nature Plan: Considering quality of life, climate and biodiversity together! Guidelines for implementing the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 in urban areas](#). Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (BfN).
- ⁹¹ See European Commission. (2020). p. 5, 13.
- ⁹² See Wong, N. H., Tan, C. L., Kolokotsa, D. D., & Takebayashi, H., (2021). [Greenery as a mitigation and adaptation strategy to urban heat](#). *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 2(3), 166–181, p. 166.
- ⁹³ See Iodice, S., Arbau, L., Maistrali, A., Marando, F., Melchiorri, M., Proietti, P., Sulis, P., Tainguy, O., & Vandecasteele, I., (2024). [EU cities and heat extremes \(Report No. JRC137891\)](#). European Commission, figure 1 – Urban Heat Island intensity per city, p. 3.

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- ⁹⁴ See Met Éireann. (2026). [Climate statement for January 2026](#). 2 February and Nazeri Tahroudi, M., (2025). [Comprehensive global assessment of precipitation trend and pattern variability considering their distribution dynamics](#). *Scientific Reports*, 15, 22458, p. 2.
- ⁹⁵ See Pinto, H., Elston, J., Sunday, O. S., & Nogueira, C. (2026). [From Concept to Practice: Evidence and Lessons from Sponge City Implementation in Shenzhen, China](#). *Urban Science*, 10(3), 135, p. 5.
- ⁹⁶ See Ahmed, H. G., Aziz, S. Q., Wu, B., Ahmed, M. S., Jha, K., Wang, Z., Nie, Y., & Huang, T. (2024). [Application of sponge city for controlling surface runoff pollution](#). *Asian Journal of Environment & Ecology*, 23(9), 1–23, see figure 1, p.6.
- ⁹⁷ See Ahmed *et al.* (2024), p. 2-3.
- ⁹⁸ See Ahmed *et al.* (2024), p. 3.
- ⁹⁹ See Pinto, H., Elston, J., Sunday, O. S., & Nogueira, C. (2026). [From concept to practice: Evidence and lessons from Sponge City implementation in Shenzhen, China](#). *Urban Science*, 10(3), 135, p. 1, 22 and *passim*.
- ¹⁰⁰ See Yu, K., Gies, E., & Wood, W. W. (2025). [To solve climate change, we need to restore our Sponge Planet](#). *Nature Water*, 3, 4–6, p. 1-3.
- ¹⁰¹ See Wang, J., Zhou, W., McPhearson, T., Cook, E. M., Herreros-Cantis, P., & Liu, J. (2025). [Socio-ecological impacts of the investment of urban nature in heat mitigation for two megacities](#). *Earth's Future*, 13(6), p. 1, 10, *passim*.
- ¹⁰² See Finnerty, P. B., Carthey, A. J. R., Banks, P. B., Brewster, R., Grueber, C. E., Houston, D., Martin, J. M., McManus, P., Roncolato, F., van Eeden, L. M., Wauchope, M., & Newsome, T. M. (2025). [Urban rewilding to combat global biodiversity decline](#). *BioScience*, 75(7), 545–558, p. 545, 548, 553, *passim*.
- ¹⁰³ See Waniek, M., Castanho, R. A., Franco, M., Rincón, V., & Velázquez, J. (2026). [Bibliographic Review on Transnational Cooperation in Environmental Issues in European Countries \(2010–2025\)](#). *Earth*, 7(1), 2, p. 8,14, *passim*.
- ¹⁰⁴ See Liczner, A. R., Pither, R., Bennett, J. R., Bowman, J., Hall, K. R., Fletcher, R. J. Jr, Ford, A. T., Michalak, J. L., Rayfield, B., Wittische, J., & Pither, J. (2024). [Advances and challenges in ecological connectivity science](#). *Ecology and Evolution*, 14, e70231, p. 2 and 9.
- ¹⁰⁵ See Wadden Sea Flyway Initiative. (n.d.). [Flyway conservation](#).
- ¹⁰⁶ See Marcacci, G., *et al.* (2023) [A roadmap integrating research, policy, and actions to conserve Afro-Palaearctic migratory landbirds at a flyway scale](#). *Conservation Letters*, Jan/Feb Vol 16, Issue1, p .2.
- ¹⁰⁷ See British Trust for Ornithology. (n.d.). [Cuckoo tracking project](#).
- ¹⁰⁸ The NPWS joined the BTO Cuckoo team to satellite track four Irish Cuckoos. Source [NPWS](#).
- ¹⁰⁹ See Cuckoo migration map at British Trust for Ornithology. (n.d.). [Cuckoo tracking project – Volunteers](#), map copied on 2 April 2026. For further information on the tracking project see: [Tracking 42 male Common Cuckoo during 56 autumn migrations 2011-2014](#). Diagram by Nigel Hawtin. See also Hewson, C. *et al.* (2016) [Population decline is linked to migration route in the Common Cuckoo](#), *Nature Communications* 7, 12296.
- ¹¹⁰ See Birdwatch Ireland on the [Sedge Warbler](#) and [Wheatear](#).
- ¹¹¹ See Bernardo-Madrid, R., González-Suárez, M., Rosvall, M. *et al.* (2025) [A general rule on the organization of biodiversity in Earth's biogeographical regions](#), *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, vol. 9, pp. 1193–1204, p. 1193). The following source talks about plural (mis)understandings about bioregions being a seemingly established concept: Wearne, S., *et al.* (2023) [A learning journey into contemporary bioregionalism](#), *People & Nature*, vol. 5, no. 6, p 2124-2140.
- ¹¹² See Wearne *et al.* (2023) p 2124-2140 and One Earth's 2023 [Bioregions Framework Map](#) created by intersecting biomes with large-scale topographic features and ecoregional groupings to delineate 185 discrete bioregions of the world.
- ¹¹³ See One Earth. (2023). [Bioregions 2023: Nature's map of the Earth](#).
- ¹¹⁴ See One Earth. (n.d.). [Great Britain, Ireland & Faroe Islands \(PA9\)](#).

¹¹⁵ See Nordic Council of Ministers. (n.d.). [The Nordic Council of Ministers](#). Nordic Co-operation and some of its work on [biodiversity](#) and [climate](#). The Faroe Islands are about 750 Km to the northern tip of Ireland and closer to the coastal edge of Iceland (520 km), Norway (640 km) and the Shetland Islands (360 km). Approximate distances taken from [Google Maps](#).

¹¹⁶ See the *Life of Saint Columba* by Adomnán of Iona, an Irish monk living on the Inner Hebridean island. See Adamnan, S. (1905). [The life of Saint Columba \(Columbkille\) A.D. 521–597](#) (W. Huyshe, Trans.). George Routledge & Sons. (Original work published ca. 697–700), p.6.

See also Xu, H. (2022). [Terminology of the British Isles](#). In *Encyclopaedia*. November 3.

¹¹⁷ See European Environment Agency. (2020). [State of nature in the EU: Results from reporting under the nature directives 2013–2018](#) (EEA Report No. 10/2020). p. 5, 34, 41, 72, 74, 101. The *State of Nature in the EU* report is produced on the basis of six-year reporting cycles and rely on data submitted by member states under the Birds and Habitats Directives. The above 2020 report covered the period 2013–2018. The next one will cover the period 2019–2024 and is expected towards the end of 2026. This report will be particularly important as it will provide the first major assessment of whether the EU is on track to meet its 2030 Biodiversity Strategy targets and the requirements of the Nature Restoration Law.

¹¹⁸ See European Environment Agency. (2020). p. 72, p.74, 87, figure 4.24.

¹¹⁹ See European Environment Agency. (2020). p. 92-3.

¹²⁰ See EU Commission (2020) [Biodiversity Strategy for 2030: Bringing Nature Back into our Lives](#), Brussels, 20 May, COM (2020) 380 final, p: 2-3, 4, 6.

¹²¹ See ECO-UNESCO. (n.d.). [Biodiversity](#) and Tolmé, P., (2017) [The U.S. Biodiversity Crisis: A surprising number and variety of North American wildlife species are quietly disappearing](#), *Conservation* January 30, van Goethem, T., & van Zanden, J. L., (2021) [Biodiversity trends in a historical perspective](#) in *How was Life*, Vol 2, OECD, page 218 and National Academies of Sciences, Engineering & Medicine (2022) [Biodiversity at Risk: Today's Choices Matter](#), Washington, DC: The National Academies Press, p. 1.

¹²² See Lennon, M. (2024). [Confronting the politics of unsustainability in Ireland's Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss](#), *Planning Theory & Practice*, 25(1), 131–136, p. 131.

¹²³ See Rittel, H. W. J., & Webber, M. M., (1973). [Dilemmas in a general theory of planning](#). *Policy Sciences*, 4(2), 155–169, see p. 155, 160-161 on the above.

¹²⁴ See Bannink, D., Sancino, A., & Sorrentino, M., (2024). [Governance without we. Wicked problems and collaborative governance](#). *Public Policy and Administration*, 39(3), 301-323.

¹²⁵ See Daviter, F., (2019). [Policy analysis in the face of complexity: What kind of knowledge to tackle wicked problems?](#) *Teaching Public Administration*, 37(1), 62–83. *passim*

Daviter's type of viewpoint has developed today to a realisation that wicked problems require a type of analytical humility and a shift from solving the problem to dealing with or taming it as best we can and has moved from a niche academic argument to an important element of global climate and biodiversity strategy.

¹²⁶ See European Commission (2019) [Attitudes of Europeans towards Biodiversity](#), Special Eurobarometer 481 Report, May, p. 4-5.

¹²⁷ See European Commission (2022) [Standard Eurobarometer 96 Winter 2021-2022: Public opinion in the European Union, First results](#), Fieldwork: January-February 2022, p. 23. In the US people's priorities range from the economy at 71% down through health, COVID, education, social security, terrorism, and down to climate change in 14th place (42%) but there is no mention of nature or biodiversity. See Pew Research Centre (2022) [Public's Top Priority for 2022: Strengthening the Nation's Economy](#), 16 February, p. 4.

¹²⁸ See Toynbee, A. J., (1987) [A Study of History: Abridgement of Vols I-VI Paperback](#), Oxford University Press. See also Schmandt, J and Ward, C. H., (2000), ['Challenge and Response'](#) in Schmandt, J. and Ward, C. H., (Eds) [Sustainable Development: The Challenge of Transition](#), Cambridge University Press.

Toynbee argues that national states are not intelligible fields of study and identifies five living civilizations from the original twenty-one he listed: Western Christendom (Western Civilization), Orthodox Christendom (the Byzantine/Russian world), Islamic Society, Hindu Society, Far Eastern Society. Toynbee's work has

also had its detractors including Peter Geyl who described it as 'metaphysical speculations dressed up as history'. See Bod, R. (2013). [A new history of the humanities: The search for principles and patterns from antiquity to the present](#). Oxford University Press, note 45, p. 262. Regardless of Bod's rather curt comment, what is also important today is that Toynbee's experience with war was the primary catalyst for *A Study of History*. He said he had 'grown up in the illusion that I was going to live out my life in a rational, orderly, and peaceful world. It was not until August 1914 ... that I became aware of the practical reason for studying history comprehensively. It was the outbreak of the First World War that awoke me up to the awareness of the realities. ... In August 1914 it flashed on my mind that the fifth-century historian Thucydides had foreseen that his generation's great war would be epoch-making for his world ... I now saw that classical Greek history and modern Western history were, in terms of experience, contemporary with each other. Their courses ran parallel. ... Thucydides in August 1914 had given me a shock that I am feeling still.' See Toynbee, A. J., & Caplan, J., (1972). [A study of history \(New one-volume ed., rev. and abridged\)](#). Oxford University Press; Thames & Hudson, p. 11.

¹²⁹ Both 'individual perceived autonomy and opportunity and choice enhancing societal conditions increase individual life satisfaction' and 'perceived autonomy always strongly positively influences ... life satisfaction'. See Steckermeier, L. C., (2021) [The Value of Autonomy for the Good Life. An Empirical Investigation of Autonomy and Life Satisfaction in Europe](#), *Social Indicators Research*, vol. 154, ps. 715 and 713.

¹³⁰ See Veríssimo, D. *et al.* (2024) [Changing Human Behaviour to Conserve Biodiversity](#) *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, vol. 49:419–4.

¹³¹ On the definitions and the discussion see: Martin, L., White, M. P., Hunt, A., Richardson, M., Pahl S., Burt, J. (2020) [Nature contact, nature connectedness and associations with health, wellbeing and pro-environmental behaviours](#), *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, vol. 68, who say 'nature connectedness refers to an individual's subjective sense of their relationship with the natural world'. See also Schultz, P. W. (2002). [Inclusion with nature: The psychology of human-nature relations](#) in P. Schmuck & W. P. Schultz (Eds.), *Psychology of sustainable development* (pp. 62–78). Norwell, MA: Kluwer Academic, p. 67. In addition, on the discussion and determinants and nature connectedness see: Richardson, M., Lengieza, M., White, M.P. *et al.* (2026). [Macro-level determinants of nature connectedness: An exploratory analysis of 61 countries](#). *Ambio* 55, 80–100, p. 80.

¹³² See Soga, M., and Gaston K. J., (2023) [Nature benefit hypothesis: Direct experiences of nature predict self-reported pro-biodiversity behaviours](#), *Conservation Letters*, vol. 16, issue 3.

¹³³ See Wildling. (n.d.). [Wildling: The nature app | Find nature near you](#). See also Liggins, J. (2025). [New wildling app launches connecting Yorkshire residents with nature](#). *The Yorkshire Post*. July 9 and Scott, W. (2025). [Is this new nature-connecting app the solution to the summer holiday slog?](#) *Country & Town House*, August.

¹³⁴ See Phi-Yen Nguyen *et al.* (2023) [Effect of nature prescriptions on cardiometabolic and mental health, and physical activity: a systematic review](#), *The Lancet Planetary Health*, vol. 7, issue 4.

¹³⁵ See S T Børresen *et al.* (2022), [The role of education in biodiversity conservation: Can knowledge and understanding alter locals' views and attitudes towards ecosystem services?](#) *Environmental Education Research*, 29(1), 148–163. See also J Rode *et al.* [National biodiversity strategies under-utilize the potential for individual behaviour change](#), *Environmental Science & Policy*, vol. 162.

¹³⁶ See Mann, J *et al.* (2022) [Getting Out of the Classroom and Into Nature: A Systematic Review of Nature-Specific Outdoor Learning on School Children's Learning and Development](#), *Frontiers in Public Health*, 16 May.

¹³⁷ See for example, UNEP-WCMC (2020) [Biodiversity-Related Capacity Building: Informing the preparation of a long-term strategic framework for capacity building beyond 2020](#), Cambridge, UK and T. Campagnaro *et al.* (2022) [Capacity development challenges and solutions for Natura 2000: an approach through blended learning](#). *Oryx*, 56 (5):764-773.

¹³⁸ See Fernández-I-Marín, X. *et al.* (2024) [Bureaucratic Quality and the Gap between Implementation Burden and Administrative Capacities](#), *American Political Science Review*, 118(3):1240-1260.

¹³⁹ See Ansell, C., *et al.* (2022) [Public administration and politics meet turbulence: The search for robust governance responses](#), *Public Administration*, 2023;101:3–22, p 4-5.

¹⁴⁰ See TSI 2025 Flagship – [Supporting the Resilience of Natural Resources](#) (European Commission technical support project).

In Ireland, there are a number important developments for example: The Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage (2023) [New Nature Skills Training to boost biodiversity action](#) pilot; The National Biodiversity Data Centre (2024) [New Training Framework](#); NPWS (2025) [Biodiversity Duty Reporting Guidance for Public Bodies](#) indicates areas of opportunity within public bodies where biodiversity can be incorporated, and sets out how biodiversity duty can be strengthened through clear targets, knowledge and skills development.

¹⁴¹ See Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), & World Meteorological Organization (WMO). (2026). [European state of the climate 2025 report](#), 29 April, p. 143, 145, 147, and 158. See also p. 151- Figure 19.6. More information on these cases can be found here: Copernicus Climate Change Service. (2026). [European State of the Climate 2025: Key events](#).

¹⁴² See [Birdwatch Ireland](#), [Royal Society for the Protection of Birds](#) and [British Trust for Ornithology](#).

¹⁴³ See [Straits Research](#) and Business Wire (2025) [Ireland Construction Industry Report 2025](#), June. Recently, the Irish government published its updated National Development Plan, committing €275.4 billion of public capital investment to 2035 in sectors such as housing, water, transport, health, education, education, climate and energy. See Government of Ireland (2025) [National Development Plan Review 2025](#): Project Ireland, 22 July.

¹⁴⁴ See Chartered Institute of Ecology & Environmental Management (2024) [Biodiversity Net Gain in Ireland](#), August, CIEEM Ireland Policy Group and PAS (2024) [Local Government Planning Advisory Service \(2024\) Biodiversity Net Gain FAQs](#). This was also discussed in the Citizen's Assembly on Biodiversity – see Lennon, M. (2024). [Confronting the politics of unsustainability in Ireland's Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss. Planning Theory & Practice](#), 25(1), 131–136, p. 135.

¹⁴⁵ See Mammides, C. Campos-Arceiz, A., (2025) [Media coverage of biodiversity falls short compared to climate change and popular culture](#). *NPJ Biodiversity* 4, 11. See BBC Studios. (n.d.). [The Natural History Unit](#).

¹⁴⁶ See for example, Laffoley D., *et al.* (2020) [Evolving the narrative for protecting a rapidly changing ocean, post-COVID-19](#), *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, vol. 31, Issue 6;1–23 and Pralle, S. B., (2009) [Agenda-setting and climate change](#), *Environmental Politics*, 18(5), 781–799.

¹⁴⁷ See OECD Observatory of Public Sector Innovation. (2016). [The Irish Citizens' Assembly](#), 17 December and Lennon, M., (2024). [Confronting the politics of unsustainability in Ireland's Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss. Planning Theory & Practice](#), 25(1), 131–136, p. 131

¹⁴⁸ See [Citizens Assembly on Biodiversity Loss](#) and [National Parks & Wildlife Services](#) Nov. 2024. See also the [Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action Report on the examination of recommendations of the Citizens' Assembly report on biodiversity loss](#) and, in particular, its conclusions and recommendation.

¹⁴⁹ Citizen's Assemblies are underpinned by 'sortition', the practice of delegating public decision-making to randomly selected panels. This is a method of choosing members through a random lottery that provides representative groups who deliberate on complex public issues and provide policy recommendations. This was the primary method of choosing officials in Ancient Athenian democracy and in medieval and Renaissance republics like Venice and Florence to prevent powerful families from monopolizing control and to reduce corruption. Recent articles have discussed the selection process and how to improve it. See for example, Gąsiorowska, A. (2023). [Sortition and its principles: Evaluation of the selection processes of citizens' assemblies](#). *Journal of Deliberative Democracy*, 19(1), p. 1, 8-9. See also Brustle, J., Fioravanti,

S., Ponitka, T., and Vollen, J., (2025) [The Panel Complexity of Sortition: Is 12 Angry Men Enough?](#) arXivLabs, submission: 29 April and A Assos *et al.* (2025) [Alternates, Assemble! Selecting Optimal Alternates for Citizens' Assemblies](#), arXivLabs, submission: 2 June, p. 1.

¹⁵⁰ See R Wells (2021) [Are citizen juries and assemblies on climate change driving democratic climate policymaking? An exploration of two case studies in the UK](#), Climate Change, 16 September. See also Walsh C. D. and Elkind J. A., (2021) [The dissatisfied and the engaged: citizen support for citizens' assemblies and their willingness to participate](#), *Irish Political Studies*, vol. 36, no. 4, 647–666 which suggests that participation rates in Citizens' Assemblies will be lower among some groups than others and are influenced by such factors as education, political interest, and perceived corruption. And Carroll, R. (2024) [Irish referendum fiasco puts future of lauded citizens' assemblies in doubt, 20 March](#), *The Guardian*.

¹⁵¹ See Government of Ireland (2024) [Ireland's 4th National Biodiversity Action Plan 2023–2030](#), Department of Housing, Housing & Heritage, Jan, p. 1, 7-8, 58 and *passim*. Here the aim is to ensure that everyone has an awareness of biodiversity and its importance, and of the implications of its loss, while also understanding how they can act to address the biodiversity emergency as part of a renewed national effort to 'act for nature'. See p. 23.

¹⁵² See O'Donohoe, S. and Sheenan, L. (2025). [Mobilising Finance for Biodiversity: Insights From Across the Island of Ireland](#). *Accounting, Finance & Governance Review*, 33, p. 2.

¹⁵³ See World Wildlife Fund. (n.d.). [NBSAP tracker: Check your country's nature progress](#).

¹⁵⁴ See OECD. (2025). [Environmental outlook on the triple planetary crisis: Stakes, evolution and policy linkages](#) (OECD Environmental Outlook). OECD Publishing, Paris, p. 376 – 377. See also (OECD). (2025) [Government at a Glance 2025](#), OECD Publishing, Paris. p. 84.

¹⁵⁵ See OECD. (2025). [OECD Policy Coherence Scan of Ireland: Strengthening Institutional Mechanisms for Sustainable Development](#), OECD Publishing, Paris, p. 10, 113, 119, 141, *passim*.

¹⁵⁶ This point is covered in a more nuanced way by Kennedy, K. A., Giblin, T., & McHugh, D. (1988). [The economic development of Ireland in the twentieth century](#), London, Routledge. See section 1.1.2 and *passim*. In 1.1.2 Kennedy asks 'why did Ireland not succeed in developing a larger industrial base' in the early 1920s? He says here that 'among the larger European countries, regions as big as Ireland remained industrially undeveloped', having explained that at the time Ireland had been a region within the United Kingdom. And even if we were to view Ireland as a separate country, the 'level of industrial development in the country as a whole was not uniquely low' at that time and 'was the same order as some other European countries at the time, such as Italy, Spain and Portugal.'

¹⁵⁷ See Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). [New Ireland Forum](#). In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved February 12, 2026, Coakley, J., (2022) [A Farewell to Northern Ireland? Constitutional Options for Irish Unity](#), *The Political Quarterly*, March, the Stationery Office (1984) [New Ireland Forum Report](#), 2 May (preface ch. 1 sec. 1.1) and Connolly, E. and Doyle, J., (2015) [Ripe moments for Exiting Political Violence: an Analysis of the Northern Ireland Case](#), *Irish Studies in International Affairs*, vol. 26, pp. 147-162, p. 154.

¹⁵⁸ See the Stationery Office (1984) [New Ireland Forum Report](#), 2 May.

¹⁵⁹ See MacDonagh, O., (1985) [What Was New in the New Ireland Forum?](#) *The Crane Bag*, vol. 9, no. 2, Irish Ideologies, pp. 166-170; Murphy, J., Denyer, D., Pettigrew, A. (2021). [The Role of Framing Mechanisms in Explaining System-Wide Change: The Case of the Northern Ireland Conflict and Peace Process](#), *British Journal of Management*, vol. 32, 322–341, p. 329; [Seanad Éireann debate](#) (1984), Tuesday, 30 Oct vol. 105 no. 12; [New Ireland Forum Report](#) (1984), The Stationery Office; Irish Times MRBI All-Ireland Poll on the New Ireland Forum in the Department of the Taoiseach. (1984). [Note of a meeting between the Taoiseach and the British Prime Minister, Margaret Thatcher, at Chequers, 19 November 1984](#) (TSCH/2014/105/822; Anglo-Irish Relations - General). National Archives of Ireland, Dublin, Ireland. Conflict Archive on the Internet (CAIN), p 1, 2, Table 1: Awareness of and rating of usefulness of New Ireland Forum.

¹⁶⁰ See Hayward, K. (2004). [The politics of nuance: Irish official discourse on northern Ireland](#). *Irish Political Studies*, 19(1), 18–38, p. 24, Coakley, J. (2017). [Adjusting to partition: from irredentism to “consent” in twentieth-century Ireland](#). *Irish Studies Review*, 25(2), 193–214, p. 198 and Smyth, T. (2015, November 14). [New Ireland Forum helped begin process of changing hearts and minds](#). *The Irish Times*.

¹⁶¹ See Murphy, J., Denyer, D., and Pettigrew, A. (2021). [The role of framing mechanisms in explaining system wide change: The case of the Northern Ireland conflict and peace process](#). *British Journal of Management*, 32(1), 125–144. p. 323, 329, 333, 336-338.

¹⁶² See Dawson, N. M., *et al.* (2024) [Reviewing the science on 50 years of conservation: Knowledge production bias es and lessons for practice](#), *Ambio* 53, 1395–1413. See p. 1404. See also Langhammer, P. F., *et al.* (2024) [The positive impact of conservation action](#), *Science*, pp. 453-458.

¹⁶³ See Hickman, C., *et al.* (2021) [Climate anxiety in children and young people and their beliefs about government responses to climate change: a global survey](#), *The Lancet Planetary Health*, vol. 5, issue 12, p. e863. Learned helplessness, according to another study, acts as a barrier to pro-environmental behaviour in the face of environmental concerns. This refers to 'eco-anxiety' where some people feel helpless and frustrated due to their inability to make a difference in stopping climate change. See Landry, N., *et al.* (2018) [Learned helplessness moderates the relationship between environmental concern and behaviour](#), *Environmental Psychology*, vol. 55. Finally, Dock talks about the impact of the climate and ecological challenge on mental health and discusses what she refers to as ecological grief which often manifests as helplessness, despair, and anxiety. See Dock, E., (2025). [Ecological grief in Bangladesh’s mental health landscape](#), *Innovative Health Research*, 1(1), 14-16.

¹⁶⁴ A proposal to use the forum mechanism on the unemployment problem was made at a major conference on unemployment in 1986. Although supported by the Irish Congress of Trade Unions, Irish National Organisation of the Unemployed, Combat Poverty Agency and a number of political parties it was not established. See Combat Poverty Agency (1992) [Making Social Rights a Reality](#), Submission to the Minister for Social Welfare on the 1992 Budget, p 18, footnote 25 and related text. See also Kerins, A. T., Ed. (1988): [Unemployment: the need for change](#), Boole Press, chapter 16 and Kerins A., (1991) [The Jobs Forum: Its Eventual Arrival?](#) *Administration*, vol. 39, no.3, pp. 248-264.

¹⁶⁵ Lecky says history is valuable when it allows us, ‘standing as on a height, to look beyond the smoke and turmoil of our petty quarrels, and detect in the slow developments of the past the great permanent forces that are steadily bearing nations onwards to improvement or decay’. See Lecky, W., E., H. (1892) [The Political Value off History](#), London, Edward Arnold, p. 53-54.

¹⁶⁶ See Waniek, M., Castanho, R. A., Franco, M., Rincón, V., & Velázquez, J. (2026). [Bibliographic Review on Transnational Cooperation in Environmental Issues in European Countries](#) (2010–2025). *Earth*, 7(1), 2, p. 1, 13-14 *passim*. (This also discuss air and water pollution and waste management.). See also

¹⁶⁷ On the above definition see for example: Persson, J., Qin, S., & Zaehring, J. G. (2022). [Patterning conservation flows: How formal and informal networks shape transnational conservation practice](#). *Conservation and Society*, 20(3), 245–256, p. 246; on transnational conservation networks see: Chauvier-Mendes, Y., Pollock, L.J., Verburg, P.H. *et al.* [Transnational conservation to anticipate future plant shifts in Europe](#). *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 8, 454–466 (2024), p. 454 and on contracts see: Affolder, N. (2012). [Transnational conservation contracts](#). *Leiden Journal of International Law*, 25(2), 443–460, p. 444.

¹⁶⁸ On the above see Vasiljević, M., Zunckel, K., McKinney, M., Erg, B., Schoon, M., Rosen Michel, T. (2015). [Transboundary Conservation: A systematic and integrated approach](#). Best Practice Protected Area Guidelines Series No. 23, Gland, Switzerland: IUCN. xii + 107 pp, p. v, ix, xi, 35 and *passim*; Wang L, Ali SH, Thornton DH and Farhadinia MS (2024) [Editorial: Transboundary conservation](#). *Frontiers in Conservation Science*, vol. 5, January, p.1-2 and Bresadola, M., & Bjärhall, A. (2025). [Analysis report on how to implement and sustain long-term transnational biodiversity monitoring schemes](#) (Version v1: publication date 30 June) [Report]. Zenodo, p. 7, 25.

¹⁶⁹ Along with creative industries, drugs and alcohol, early years, energy, housing, indigenous, minority and lesser-used languages, planning and places, social inclusion, transport, environment and invasive species. See British-Irish Council. (n.d.). [Home](#).

¹⁷⁰ See British-Irish Council. (n.d.). [Environment](#).

¹⁷¹ On the above see British-Irish Council. (n.d.). [About the BIC](#). See also British-Irish Council. (2025). [British-Irish Council annual report 2024–2025](#), p. 6, and British-Irish Council. (2024). [Planning and places ministerial final communiqué](#), 8 November, p. 1-2.

¹⁷² On the above, see Tannam, E. and Kelly, C. J. (2022). [Brexit and the Belfast/Good Friday Agreement's three strands](#). *The Journal of Cross Border Studies in Ireland*, 17, 90–104, p. 92. They say the BIC 'lacks any substantive role in managing relations across these islands, remaining curiously stagnant since 1998 despite the deepening of the devolution settlement in Scotland and Wales', see p. 95.

The British-Irish Intergovernmental Conference was also established under the Good Friday Agreement. In contrast to the BIC it deals with bilateral relations between both governments and provides a framework for regular, high-level meetings, often regarding Northern Ireland affairs. In this respect it serves as a high level forum for cooperation on security, terrorism, paramilitarism, and other cross-border matters. See Department of Foreign Affairs. (2024, April 29). [British-Irish Intergovernmental Conference \(BIIGC\) April joint communiqué](#) and Cabinet Office & Northern Ireland Office. (2025, November). [British-Irish Intergovernmental Conference \(BIIGC\) joint communiqué](#): GOV.UK.

¹⁷³ See Department of Further & Higher Education, Research, Innovation & Science. (2023). [Minister Harris, Secretary of State Donelan and Permanent Secretary Godfrey announce €70 million for research centres](#), 28 November; Department of Further & Higher Education, Research, Innovation & Science. (2022). [Ministers Harris, Ghani and Poots announce joint investment in co-centres for research and innovation](#). Government of Ireland, 24 October. Department of Foreign Affairs. (2023); [British-Irish Intergovernmental Conference \(BIIGC\) November 2023 joint communiqué](#); Government of Ireland, November 28; Co-Centre for Climate + Biodiversity + Water. (n.d.). [Co-Centre for Climate + Biodiversity + Water](#).

¹⁷⁴ See Rood, J. and Victor, J. (2019, February 25). [Nordic Council and Nordic Council of Ministers](#) (Revised 2025, November 24). Nordics.info; Aarhus University.

¹⁷⁵ For the above, including the data, see Burns, F., Mordue, S., al Fulaij, N., Boersch-Supan, P. H., Boswell, J., Boyd, R. J., Bradfer-Lawrence, T., de Ornellas, P., de Palma, A., de Zylva, P., Dennis, E. B., Foster, S., Gilbert, G., Halliwell, L., Hawkins, K., Haysom, K. A., Holland, M. M., Hughes, J., ... & Gregory, R. D. (2023). [State of Nature 2023](#), State of Nature Partnership, p. 3-4, 7, 19.

¹⁷⁶ See Joint Nature Conservation Committee & Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs. (2025.). [UK biodiversity indicators 2025](#), 2 December, and Brotherton, P. (2023.). [State of Nature \[Blog post\]](#). Natural England Blog. 29 September.

¹⁷⁷ See NASA Earth Observatory. (2019). [Tracking Amazon deforestation from above](#), 20 December; NASA Earth Observatory. (2024). [Heat stress on the Great Barrier Reef](#). 18 March; NASA (n.d.) [Fire Information for Resource Management System \(FIRMS\)](#), retrieved 20 March 2026; NASA Science Editorial Team. (2023.). [A global biodiversity crisis: How NASA satellites help track changes to life on Earth](#), NASA, 29 May.

¹⁷⁸ On the above see Helliwell, J. F., Layard, R., and Sachs, J. D. (Eds.). (2013). [World happiness report 2013](#). Sustainable Development Solutions Network, p. 17, 56, 62, 83-84.

¹⁷⁹ See Kang, Y., Kim, BY., Lee, D. (2025) [Political polarization, state capacity, and economic growth](#), *Economic Systems*, 49, 4, p. 1, 13.

¹⁸⁰ See Muringani, J., Fitjar, R.D. & Rodríguez-Pose, A. (2024). [Political trust and economic development in European regions](#). *The Annals of Regional Science*, 73, 2059–2089, p. 2059, 2078-2079.

They also say that although the 'results expose a direct and positive connection between political trust and both social trust and government quality. These relationships are not linear, demonstrating diminishing

returns. This underscores the importance of reaching a certain threshold of both social trust and government quality for political trust to thrive within regions.' p. 2079.

¹⁸¹ See Hashim, Z., Fidrmuc, J., Ghosh, S. (2025). [Political parties' ideological bias and convergence in economic outcomes](#), *European Journal of Political Economy*, Volume 87, 102669, p. 1, 2, 15.

¹⁸² See United Nations. (1999). [The world at six billion](#). Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, p. 8 and Worldometer. (n.d.). [World population clock: 2026 world population](#), retrieved May 8, 2026.

¹⁸³ See Steffen, W., Broadgate, W., Deutsch, L., Gaffney, O., & Ludwig, C. (2015). [The trajectory of the Anthropocene: The Great Acceleration](#), *The Anthropocene Review*, 2(1), 81–98, p. 82 and 92.

¹⁸⁴ See Steffen, W., *et al.* (2015), p. 81, 82, 84, 86, figure 1 and 2. The top three diagrams taken from figure 2 p. 84 contain three coloured splits for the OECD and BRICS countries, and the rest of the world.

¹⁸⁵ Email received from R Dunphy, information Security Governance, Risk and Compliance Senior Manager TU Dublin, 27 Jan. 2026. On attack surfaces see, for example, Fortinet. (n.d.). [What is an attack surface? Definition and how to reduce it](#), retrieved 1 May 2026.

¹⁸⁶ Economic decisions can affect people not directly involved in the transactions. Sometimes these indirect effects are tiny. But when they are large they can be problematic—what economists call externalities. In this context, an externality can be defined as the indirect effects of the economic activities on others, but the price of the product does not take these externalities into account. As a result, there are differences between private returns or costs and the returns or costs to society as a whole. See Helbling, T. (2010). [What are externalities?](#) *Finance & Development*, 47(4). December, International Monetary Fund, p. 48

¹⁸⁷ See ScienceDirect. (n.d.). [Ecological vulnerability](#). In [Earth and planetary sciences topics](#), retrieved April 30, 2026, AI generated definition based on: [Ecological Indicators, 2023](#).

¹⁸⁸ See Dublin City Council. (2022). [Dublin City Council annual report & accounts 2022](#), p.3. For example, 12 of its parks won Green Flag awards in 2025 – see Dublin City Council. (2025). [Dublin City Council adopted revenue budget 2026](#), p. 62. See also Dublin City Council. (2026). [Annual service delivery plan 2026](#), p. 22 which summarises the parks, landscape and biodiversity delivery plan.

¹⁸⁹ See Dublin City Council. (2021). [Dublin City Biodiversity Action Plan 2021–2025](#). Dublin City Council, p. 24.

¹⁹⁰ My father was amazed when he first visited St Anne's Park and continued calling it 'wonderful' every time he returned. He grew up in rural Mayo and realised just how nice it was.

¹⁹¹ See Dublin City Council. (2021). [Discovery Centre update report to area committee](#), May, p. 1.

¹⁹² See O'Dúlaing, D. (2018). [Presentation on UNESCO Dublin Bay Discovery Centre](#) [PowerPoint slides]. Dublin City Council, Community, Gaeilge, Sport, Arts & Culture SPC Meeting, March 12, p. 15, 17.

¹⁹³ See Dublin City Council. (2020). [North Bull Island Nature Reserve Action Plan 2020-2025 for the Implementation of Management Objectives](#), May, p. 6 and Fehily Timoney. (2024). [Local Authority Climate Action Plan: Strategic Environmental Assessment Statement](#), Commissioned by Dublin City Council, p. 19.

¹⁹⁴ See Santos-Rojo, C., Llopis-Amorós, M., Manuel García-García, J., (2023) [Overtourism and sustainability: A bibliometric study \(2018–2021\)](#), *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, vol. 188, p. 1 and Mihalic, T., (2020) [Conceptualising overtourism: A sustainability approach](#), *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 84, p. 3.

¹⁹⁵ See Mihalic, T., (2020) p. 2, 3.

¹⁹⁶ A visitor (domestic, inbound, or outbound) is classified as a *tourist* (or overnight visitor) if their trip includes an overnight stay, or as a same-day visitor (or excursionist) otherwise. See Mor, M., Dalyot, S., Ram, Y. (2023) [Who is a tourist? Classifying international urban tourists using machine learning](#), *Tourism Management*, vol. 95, p. 1.

¹⁹⁷ See Pereira Lindoso D., Boix D., Ribas A., Bou J. and Quintana X. D. (2025) [Deurbanizing for conservation and adapting: framing ecological restoration as a nature-based solution in La Pletera salt marsh, Catalonia \(Spain\)](#)ss. *Frontiers in Water*, vol. 6, p. 02, 03, 05.

¹⁹⁸ See Sandström, C., Mancheva, I., and Laudon, H. (2025) [Unlocking the potential of biosphere reserves: a review of structural, institutional, and ideational challenges to transformational learning](#), *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, vol. 75, p 1-4, *passim*.

¹⁹⁹ See Royal Horticultural Society. (2025). [RHS state of gardening report 2025](#), see p. 2 – 4, *passim*.

²⁰⁰ See Teerlinck, J., Van Meerbeek, K., Wittemans, K., Dewaelheyns, V., Raymaekers, P., Lange, F., Steen, T., Somers, B. (2026) [Exploring drivers and motivations behind garden management for climate change adaptation](#), *Land Use Policy*, vol. 165, p. 1-3, 5, 8-10.

²⁰¹ Source Google. (2026). [Gemini](#) (May 13 version) [Large multimodal model]. *Note*. The diagram was adapted from "Biodiverse & Climate resilient Garden.jpeg" provided by the author using Google Gemini (2026) to replace perimeter fencing with mixed native hedges. The original image with was found [here](#).

²⁰² See Derco, S., (2022) [Gambling on Development: Why Some Countries Win and Others Lose](#), Hurst, London, and Keo, B., Z. (2020) [Crossing the River by Feeling the Stones: Deng Xiaoping in the Making of Modern China](#), *Education About Asia: Volume 25:2: Teaching Asia's Giants: China*. See also CSO. (2022). [Census FAQ on Time Capsule](#).

²⁰³ Councillor Tom Brabazon's letter of the 9 July 2020 states that 'in regard to the Discovery Centre on Bull Island, I confirm that I have made representations to the Senior Executive Parks Superintendent, Dublin City Council, Parks, Biodiversity and Landscape Services division asking him to consider relocating the centre and I have outlined all of the various points you raised in your email. I have stressed the importance of this issue and I will come back again as soon as I receive a reply.'

²⁰⁴ For example, Gray, G. and Kendzia, V. (2009). [Organizational Self-Censorship: Corporate Sponsorship, Nonprofit Funding, and the Educational Experience](#), *Canadian Review of Sociology/Revue Canadienne de Sociologie*, vol. 46, pp. 161-177 discuss how increasing reliance on sponsorship has impacted the governance of nonprofit organizations. In the case of museums, they state that corporate sponsorship is 'the gate' through which corporate interests move into the public cultural sphere of museums resulting in increased commercialization and decreased rational critical-debate and are concerned that the growing commercial climate will alter the missions and goals of museums. (p. 162 and 173). However, Lu, J. (2016). [Fear the Government? A Meta-Analysis of the Impact of Government Funding on Nonprofit Advocacy Engagement](#), *The American Review of Public Administration*, 48(3), 203-218 finds that government funding seems not to be a significant predictor of the level of nonprofits' policy advocacy engagement and concludes that they face multiple challenges when making decisions to engage in policy activities. Today, their historical role as change agents sometimes has to be compromised by their immediate role as service providers and that 'government funding may induce nonprofits to use more insider advocacy activities to achieve their advocacy goals'. (p. 211).

²⁰⁵ See, for example, Byrne, S., (2021). [Bull Island Discovery Centre will hasten precipitous decline of its wildlife: The Centre aims to attract 55,000-60,000 visitors annually](#), *Village Magazine*, 15 November.

²⁰⁶ Rewetting raises the water table on degraded or drained bogs which helps stop carbon emissions and allows the ecosystem to recover. Paludiculture is the productive use of this wet or rewetted land for economic activities (such as growing reeds, cattails, or moss). The main purpose of rewetting is restoration. The goal of paludiculture is to create an economic return from wet land, often acting as an incentive for landowners to accept rewetting. See Nielsen, C. K., Elsgaard, L., Lærke, P.E. (2024). [Site-dependent carbon and greenhouse gas balances of five fen and bog soils after rewetting and establishment of Phalaris arundinacea paludiculture](#), *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 957; Temmink, Kristiina Lång, Renske J.E. Vroom, Jens Leifeld, Christian Fritz, Walther Zeug, Daniela Thrän, Clemens Kleinspehn R. J. M., Gaudig, G., Neubert, J., Kreyling, J., Rhymes, J. M., Evans, C. D., Kotowski, W., Nordt, A., Tanneberger, F., (2026) [Agriculture on wet peatlands: the sustainability potential of paludiculture](#), *Agricultural Systems*, vol. 231.

For example, the Great Fen in England is part of the PaluWise project and Ballaghurt Bog in Ireland comes the EU's, Palus Demos project. See European Commission (2024). [Paludiculture demonstrations providing multi-actor approaches and recommendations towards large-scale deployment in the EU](#), project factsheet,

CORDIS, September 30, and European Commission (2024). [PALUdiculture large-Scale DEMOnstrationS \(PALUS DEMOS\)](#). CORDIS, October 11.

²⁰⁷ One source defines a bioswale as a ditch with vegetation and a porous bottom. In a bioswale system, the water running off roofs, roads and other hard surfaces does not flow into the sewers but instead is led into the bioswale via above-ground gutters and/or ditches. Bioswales can be incorporated into the green infrastructure and can help enhance biodiversity and quality of life. See Atelier Groenblauw. (n.d.). [Bioswales](#). Urban Green-Blue Grids, retrieved April 26, 2026.

²⁰⁸ See WHO (2017) [Urban Green Spaces: A Brief for Action](#), October, p. 11; CSO (2019) [Urban and Rural Life in Ireland](#); Statista (2025) [Urban and rural population of Ireland from 1960-2024](#), Sep 3.

Research indicates there are disparities in access to local nature areas. For example, the percentage of grassland spaces in urban areas of Northern Ireland, Scotland and England were significantly lower among the more deprived neighbourhoods. See Ngan, T. *et al.* (2025) [Inequality in green space distribution and its association with preventable deaths across urban neighbourhoods in the UK, stratified by Index of Multiple Deprivation](#), *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, 79:102–109. In addition, the U.S. has fewer forests, streams, wetlands, and other natural places near where Black, Latino, and Asian American people live. See Rowland-Shea, J. *et al.* (2020) [The Nature Gap: Confronting Racial and Economic Disparities in the Destruction and Protection of Nature in America](#), Centre for American Progress, July, p. 2. In Ireland, a discussion about nature access and related developments can be found in McGurk, E. *et al.* (2019). [Greenways, recreational access and landowner willingness to accept: a contingent valuation study of farmers in Ireland](#), *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 62(13), 2375–2392.

There has also been some debate on the concentration of nature ownership and access in some rural areas of the U.S. See Farrell, J. (2020) [Billionaire Wilderness - the ultra-wealthy and the remaking of the American West](#), Princeton University Press. This sociological study discusses how some wealthy people are buying up pockets of nature in Teton County, Wyoming, one of the most pristine ecosystems in the world, so as to climb the socioeconomic ladder and create more virtuous and deserving versions of themselves. Teton County is both the richest and most inequitable county in the U.S (see p. 4).

²⁰⁹ See [BISE: Biodiversity Information System for Europe](#). This comprises 618 sites designated under national laws and 604 recognized as Natura 2000 sites. See also [NPWS Special Protection Areas \(SPA\)](#).

²¹⁰ See United Nations (2024) [Biodiversity – our strongest natural defence against climate change](#), (retrieved 6 Sep. 25). More generally see: Molloy, A., *et al.* (2024) [Identification and assessment of best practice in nature-based solutions for climate action and ecosystem restoration in Ireland](#), Working Paper No. 26, February, Climate Change Advisory Council, and Wilson, D., *et al.* (2022) [Carbon and climate implications of rewetting a raised bog in Ireland](#), *Global Change Biology*, Nov, 28 (21).

²¹¹ See National Trust [Project: The Wider Wicken Fen Vision](#).

²¹² See Cambridgeshire and Peterborough [Local Nature Recovery Strategy – Wider Wicken Fen Vision](#).

²¹³ See BBC (2024) [Oldest National Trust reserve Wicken Fen 'a mecca for naturalists'](#), 21 January.

²¹⁴ See Davies, N. (2016) [Cuckoo: Cheating by Nature](#), Bloomsbury.

²¹⁵ See [Future Fens Flood Risk Management – Baseline Report](#), December 2020. See also the National Trust: [The Wider Wicken Fen Vision](#) and [The History of Wicken Fen](#). See also Tegala, A. (2025). [Restoring the Past to Protect Our Future: How Wicken Fen Offers a Blueprint for Nature Recovery](#), 7 August.

²¹⁶ See IReL. (n.d.). [Who Are We?](#) and Technological University Dublin. (n.d.). [Open Access Publishing](#).